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Abstract: This work proposes an analysis of conventional (single stage) and dual stage Closed-Loop Pressure Retarded Osmosis (CLPRO) for power generation from a salinity gradient resource. Model calculations were performed taking into account the influence of operating parameters such as the draw solution concentration, membrane area, and draw solution pressure on the performance of the CLPRO process. Modeling results showed that the dual stage CLPRO process outperformed the conventional CLPRO process and power generation increased 18% by adding a second stage of PRO membrane. Multi-Effect Distillation (MED) was selected for the regeneration of the draw solution taking advantage of an available source of waste heat energy. The performance of MED process has been assessed by investigating two key parameters: the specific thermal consumption and the specific heat transfer area. The model calculations showed that the power generation by the single and dual stage CLPRO was higher than the electrical power consumption by the MED plant. In the case of the power generation obtained by the dual stage CLPRO, it was 95% higher than the electrical power consumption by the MED plant, proving the possibility of using low-grade heat for producing electricity from a salinity gradient resource.

Highlights:

1. Closed-Loop PRO (CLPRO) coupled with MED or RO for power generation
2. Single and dual stage CLPRO processes were simulated
3. RO required more electric power than MED for Draw solution regeneration
4. Dual stage CLPRO efficiency was 20% higher than the single stage CLPRO

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Dear Professor Yan

I would be grateful if you would consider the enclosed manuscript for publication in the **Journal of Applied Energy**. The paper evaluates the performance of single and dual stage Closed-loop Pressure retarded osmosis.

Best Regards,

Ali Altaee
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Letter of Response

Authors would like to thank reviewers and the editor Dr Yan for taking the time to review the paper and send their comments. We answered the reviewer's comments point by point and made the required modifications on the manuscript which appear in **RED** colour.

Reviewer #1:

The work studied the dual stage PRO in the closed-loop operation and carried out a parametric analysis of draw solution concentration, membrane area, and feed pressure. Then, two draw solution recovery methods were evaluated. There are some concerns:

1) The authors stated in Abstract, the study "taking into account the optimisation of draw solution concentration, membrane area, and feed pressure to reduce the operation and capital cost of the CLPRO process". But the optimisation or parametric analysis more focused on objectives such as power ratio, power difference, water flux, etc. As the operation and capital cost has a complex relation with these parameters and objectives, it is difficult to find how the cost varies. It will be great if the work adds a optimisation particularly focusing on the overall operational and capital cost.

Answer: Thank you very much, the objective is focused on the impact of the operation parameters on the process performance as described in line 112 in the introduction. We agree with the reviewer that an optimization focused on the operational and capital costs would be very useful to complete the analysis but the problem is the difficulty to find real economic data of labour, chemicals and power costs. They are usually confidential and vary from place to place. Therefore, the resulting errors from an economic analysis based on assumed data would be significantly high. Therefore, the study also provided an estimate of energy and membrane area requirements for the PRO process which will be reflected on the capital cost.

2) Based on energy conservation, energy recovered from CLPRO will be definitely less than that used in draw regeneration due to many reasons. In electricity-driven process such as RO, electricity consumed in RO will be larger than that regenerated by CLPRO. In thermal-driven process such as MED, MD, MSF, total energy consumed in draw recovery will be also larger than that regenerated by CLPRO. The main differences between these two scenarios are the quality of the energy input and the efficiency of the energy conversion. Thus, it is unnecessary to demonstrate the negative power balance of RO-CLPRO. And if the heat is free, all thermal desalination technologies combined with CLPRO potentially have positive power balance.

Answer: The authors have removed the RO section according to the comment of the reviewer. In the case of the thermal process, we have assumed that the thermal energy is provided by a free heat source of waste heat. Also, an electrical power consumption of 1.2 kWh/m³ has been assumed for the MED plant.

Action: Sections 2.2 and 3.3 based on RO as the regeneration system have been deleted

3) According to the schematic diagram in Fig. 1, both the draw and feed solutions are in closed-loop operation. But I did not find how the system operated? Is it in batch mode or continuous mode? How to deal with the accumulated salt leakage from draw to feed?

Answer: The system is continuous mode in which the draw solution is regenerated by MED thermal plant to produce concentrated draw solution brine and distilled water. Salt leakage can be reduced by using high rejection PRO membrane. However, in CLPRO feed solution should be purged when salt concentration increases

Action: The following sentence has been added “Notice that the CLPRO plant in Figure 1 operates in a continuous mode. Practically, the feed solution would be contaminated due to NaCl back diffusion from the DS. Therefore, the feed solution needs purging over time whereas the concentration of DS can be adjusted by adding the NaCl stock solution.”

Reviewer #2:

This paper discusses a very important problem, namely how can the energy generation be realized by closed-loop pressure retarded osmosis. This method enables the user to choose the concentration conditions in the draw and the feed phases according to demands. This paper is too long one with great number of figures. Then this does not make possible to emphasize the most important conclusion, they are lost in the long text. This manuscript was already reviewed and authors have improved it according to the reviewer's comments. Against that I give here a few critical remarks, which are recommended to be reflected in the text by the authors before publication.

Answer: Thank you; sections 2.2 and 3.3 have been removed. Authors agreed that RO regeneration is obviously requires more electrical energy than can be regenerated by the PRO. More details about the work significance were added throughout the context. Also please check point 2 of the reviewer 1

Remarks/questions:

1) The concentration difference of the selective layer can also be affected

by the external mass transfer resistance of the feed phase (low salinity water/distilled water), independently of its solute concentration, Eq. (1) does not involve this effect. Please briefly discuss why can be it made without essential error in this case.

Answer: Thank you, if reviewer means the external mass transfer resistance of solute when feed solution is facing the active layer, then we assumed that draw solution is facing the active layer to reduce the effect of concentration polarization and solute accumulation in the membrane porous layer.

Action: the following sentence has been added “PRO membrane rejection rate to monovalent ions is more than 90% which reduces solute transport across the membrane [22]. Equation 1 estimates water flux when the draw solution is facing the membrane active layer (DS-AL) to reduce the effect of internal concentration polarization and salt accumulation in the membrane porous layer.”

2) Eq. (19): why the logarithmic middle value was not used here?

Answer: Thank you, osmotic pressure of bulk draw solution is the average of inlet and outlet concentration of draw solution. Many studies estimate the osmotic pressure of bulk draw solution as the difference between the inlet and outlet concentrations of draw solution [21]. We apologize for the typing error

Action: reference has been added “We also assumed that the operating hydraulic pressure was the average osmotic pressure of π_{Fb1} and π_{Db1} , hence π_{Db1} was calculated as the following [12]”

3) Line 246: in the second stage the feed phase is not distilled one; its solute concentration can really be neglected?

Answer: As mentioned in point 2 for reviewer 1, salt back diffusion contaminates the feed solution and it will be purged when the salt concentration increases. This is an inherent issue of the CLPRO process. As such, the salt leakage will be within a narrow range which will not significantly affect the driving force across the membrane.

4) Eq. (26): it has three efficiency coefficients; what is the accuracy of this expression?

Answer: The first and second terms on the right hand of equation 26 expresses the specific power consumed for seawater filtration by the RO membrane, while the third term on the right hand side expressed power requirement for seawater pumping to the RO system. Supply pump already included in the pretreatment (Desalination, V203, 2007, 168-175). However, section 2.2 has been deleted as mentioned earlier

Action: section 2.2 has been removed

5) Table 1: what kind of membrane was used to the experiments? Parameters were determined by authors of [21]?

Answer: It has been considered the use of a cellulose triacetate FO membrane manufactured by Hydration Technology Innovations, USA . The parameters were determined from ref 21.

Action: the following sentence has been added “using cellulose triacetate FO membrane provided by Hydration Technology Innovations, USA [21]”

6) Figures contain the J_w vs. membrane area function (e.g. Figs. 5, 6, 7, etc.), mass transfer coefficient of the draw external boundary layer is constant, accordingly the function of $\exp(-J_w/k)$ does not give new results. Cannot be these figures left out?

Answer: Thank you; the mass transfer coefficient $e^{\left(\frac{-J_w}{k}\right)}$ is not constant in the full scale PRO module because draw solution dilution increases along the membrane. $e^{\left(\frac{-J_w}{k}\right)}$ is a function of J_w which changes along the membrane length in a full module PRO membrane due to draw solution dilution. Furthermore, J_w is function of the permeate flow divided by the membrane area; $J_w = Q_p/A$, which shows the impact of membrane area on water flux and concentration polarization. Reference 31 has discussed the impact of membrane area on concentration polarization and water flux. However, this issue is less obvious in flat sheet laboratory scale experiments because of the small membrane area.

7) Some inaccuracies in the text: line 539 (correctly: 3.8-3 and not 5-4 or line 543: not 0.58-0.52, but 0.48-0.35, etc.)

Answer: Thank you; authors checked the results and confirm they are correct. J_{w2} decreased from 5 to 4 L/m²h in figure 5a. In figure 5b, C_{Di2} decreased from 0.58 to 0.52 mol/L.

8) Disturbing/unpunctual drafting: „membrane flux" (e.g. line 536, 563, etc.): there is not known such kind of flux; correct expression: water flux; or: „feed pressure", line 599, 613, 891: feed phase conventionally is the low salinity phase; this expression suggests that the feed phase has the pressure, which is not true normally; most correct expression would be draw phase pressure!?

Answer: Thank you, membrane flux has been changed to water flux throughout the text. Also feed pressure was replaced by draw solution pressure.

9) Line 856: Figure 10b (there is not this figure in the text);

Answer: Thank you for picking up this typo, actually figure 11b shows S_{TC} .

Action: Figure number was corrected

10) Unfortunately, the correctness, the accuracy of the results in section 3.2 cannot be checked by the reader ?!;

Answer: Thank you; authors provided enough information about the flux, solution concentrations, flow rates and draw solution pressures of the first and second stage of the PRO process. Table 3 also shows the W_1 and W_2 at different testing conditions. These values are important because they are a function of water flux and pressure and can be used to double check the results in section 3.2

11) Abbreviation list is recommended to be given;

Answer: Abbreviation list has been provided, thank you

12) Nomenclature is also missing;

Answer: Nomenclature list has been provided as the reviewer recommended. However the length of the paper has been slightly increased

13) I also suggest the essential shortening of the figures and also the text emphasizing the most important results. This could increase the importance of the results.

Answer: Thank you, we removed sections 2.2 and 2.3 to strengthen the results as recommended by the reviewer. Figures 2, 8, 9, 10 have been removed as well.

Editors:

- An updated and complete literature review should be conducted. The relevance to Applied Energy should be enhanced with the considerations of scope and readership of the Journal.

Answer: Thank you; authors have made suitable changes to emphasize the relevance of study to the Journal of Applied energy

- A proof reading by a native English speaker should be conducted to improve both language and organization quality.

Answer: Thank you, Proof reading has been performed

- The originality of the paper needs to be further clarified. The present form does not have sufficient results to justify the novelty of a high quality journal paper.

Answer: Results have been checked and clarified, sections 2.2 and 3.3 have been removed to consolidate the results and improve the quality of the paper. Also, the different sections (especially introduction) have been modified in order to highlight the importance of the work presented in the paper and its novelty.

- The results should be further elaborated to show how they could be used for the real applications.

Answer: The results have been further discussed and elaborated in the discussion, conclusion sections

Single and Dual Stage Closed-Loop Pressure Retarded Osmosis for Power Generation: Feasibility and Performance

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Abstract

This work proposes an analysis of conventional (single stage) and dual stage Closed-Loop Pressure Retarded Osmosis (CLPRO) for power generation from a salinity gradient resource. Model calculations were performed taking into account the influence of operating parameters such as the draw solution concentration, membrane area, and draw solution pressure on the performance of the CLPRO process. Modeling results showed that the dual stage CLPRO process outperformed the conventional CLPRO process and power generation increased 18% by adding a second stage of PRO membrane. Multi-Effect Distillation (MED) was selected for the regeneration of the draw solution taking advantage of an available source of waste heat energy. The performance of MED process has been assessed by investigating two key parameters: the specific thermal consumption and the specific heat transfer area. The model calculations showed that the power generation by the single and dual stage CLPRO was higher than the electrical power consumption by the MED plant. In the case of the power generation obtained by the dual stage CLPRO, it was 95% higher than the electrical power consumption by the MED plant, proving the possibility of using low-grade heat for producing electricity from a salinity gradient resource.

Keywords: Pressure Retarded Osmosis, Dual Stage Pressure Retarded Osmosis, Osmotic Power Plant, Thermal Regeneration, Dual Stage PRO Optimization

1. Introduction:

The application of salinity gradient resource for power generation has been widely recognized as an efficient and low cost approach of renewable energy [1-8]. The most common techniques for power generation from a salinity gradient are the Pressure Retarded Osmosis (PRO) and Reverse Electrodialysis (RED) [1-14]. PRO process has attracted a lot of attention for harvesting the energy of salinity gradient because of its high efficiency and flexibility to be combined with desalination technologies such as Reverse Osmosis (RO) [6, 7, 10, 12].

45 Experimental works have demonstrated the feasibility of PRO process application
46 in a small commercial power plant [15]. Closed-Loop PRO (CLPRO) has also
47 been proposed for power generation as a heat engine but only few studies have
48 been published in this field [8, 16, 17]. Previous studies focused on the
49 performance of the PRO part and no data have been provided about the
50 performance of the entire CLPRO-thermal system. Furthermore, no studies have
51 been published yet on the potential of using closed-loop dual stage PRO process
52 for power generation.

53
54 PRO process uses osmotic energy as the driving force for power generation. A
55 high osmotic pressure draw solution (DS) is fed at one side of a semipermeable
56 membrane whereas a low osmotic pressure feed solution (FS) is pumped into the
57 opposite side of the membrane to create an osmotic pressure gradient, which
58 induces fresh water transportation towards the DS [Figure 1]. Fresh water
59 transport across the membrane will convert the chemical potential into a
60 hydraulic energy. Finally, the diluted DS is depressurized by a hydroturbine for
61 power generation. Although PRO was suggested in the seventies [18], it did not
62 receive considerable attention due to the technical limitations associated with the
63 membrane permeability and rejection rate [14-19]. Recent developments in the
64 membrane manufacturing industries have brought back the strong interest in the
65 PRO concept for power generation [19-20]. New PRO membranes have high
66 water permeability and rejection rate, which revolutionized the PRO and
67 enhanced its performance [18]. Pilot plant tests using Toyobo membrane
68 demonstrated high power density of 7.7 W/m^2 [15], which was more than the
69 theoretical recommended value (5 W/m^2) for an economic PRO process [20].
70 Furthermore, previous studies have achieved power density larger than 10 W/m^2
71 using a laboratory fabricated PRO membrane and 6%-0.06% salinity gradient
72 resource [19].

73
74 One of the operating challenges for the PRO process is the selection of a
75 suitable salinity gradient resource to create a sufficient driving force across the
76 PRO membrane. A number of salinity gradients have been suggested by
77 coupling seawater or brine from a Reverse Osmosis (RO) process with
78 wastewater effluent or fresh water [14, 15, 20-22]. It is preferable applying high
79 concentration DS to obtain high membrane flux across the PRO membrane.
80 Previous works showed that Concentration Polarization (CP) across the
81 membrane increases with increasing permeation flow and reducing the efficiency
82 of PRO process [23-25]. CP is divided into dilutive and concentrative; dilutive CP
83 occurs usually on the DS side whereas the concentrative CP occurs on the FS.
84 However, using deionized water negates the effect of concentrative CP and
85 improves the performance of PRO [23].

86
87 Closed-Loop PRO (CLPRO) has been proposed as a means for salinity gradient
88 energy capture when no natural streams are available [25]. The salinity gradient
89 resource in the CLPRO process consists of a high osmotic pressure DS and
90 deionized/low concentration FS [Figure 1A]. In this case, the diluted DS goes to a

91 regeneration unit after leaving the hydroturbine system [24]. The concentrated
92 DS and fresh water are the products of the regeneration process which are
93 recycled back to the PRO membrane. Due to the high purity of draw and feed
94 solutions, CLPRO has the advantage of reducing the PRO membrane fouling,
95 and allowing the recycling and reuse of the salinity gradient resource [8].
96 Furthermore, the osmotic pressure of the CLPRO process can be flexibly
97 designed by changing the concentration and hydraulic pressure of DS. **Figure 1**
98 **shows a schematic diagram of single and dual stage CLPRO plants which are**
99 **operated in a continuous mode. Practically, the feed solution would be**
100 **contaminated due to NaCl back diffusion from the DS. Therefore, the feed**
101 **solution needs purging over time whereas the concentration of DS can be**
102 **adjusted by adding the NaCl stock solution.**

103
104 Some recent published studies have analyzed the performance of conventional
105 PRO process in the CLPRO process [25-26]. **Dual stage PRO (DSPRO) process**
106 **has shown higher power generation potential than conventional PRO [27, 29].**
107 **The process has the potential of increasing the energy yield of salinity gradient**
108 **and reducing the membrane fouling [27, 29, 32], but no studies have investigated**
109 **its performance in a CLPRO system so far. The present study was focused on**
110 **analyzing the performance of a dual stage CLPRO process and on**
111 **demonstrating its advantages over the single stage CLPRO process. Also, the**
112 **regeneration of the draw solution by a thermal desalination process such as**
113 **Multi-effect distillation (MED) has been investigated. For this purpose, the use of**
114 **a free source of waste heat has been considered and a certain specific electricity**
115 **consumption of the MED system was assumed in the calculation of the net power**
116 **generation of the PRO process. A pre-developed computer model was applied**
117 **for optimizing the concentration and osmotic pressure of the DS, taking into**
118 **account the effect of some key operating parameters such as the draw solution**
119 **pressure, flow rates, and membrane area on the performance of the PRO**
120 **process. The PRO model was calibrated using experimental data [12] and the**
121 **PRO data outputs were taken as the inputs to the MED regeneration process for**
122 **energy calculations purposes. For the regeneration part, a computer model was**
123 **used in order to analyze the performance of MED system under several**
124 **operating conditions. The results define a baseline for the potential and feasibility**
125 **of CLPRO for power production.**

A: Single Stage

B: Dual Stage

126
127
128
129

Figure 1: Schematic diagram of closed-loop PRO system

130 2. Systems Modeling

131

132 This section describes the models used for the optimization of the PRO system
133 and the methodology used for the process simulation.

134

135 2.1 PRO system

136

137 Single and DSPRO were evaluated for a CLPRO process for power generation.
138 Figures 1A and 1B show the schematic diagram of a single and dual stage
139 CLPRO, respectively. For a single stage PRO, the membrane flux, DS
140 concentration, recovery rate and power density were optimized taking into
141 account the effect of membrane area, draw solution pressure and DS flow rate on
142 the performance of the PRO process. The following equations were applied for
143 estimating the performance and the power generation of a single stage CLPRO
144 process [23]. Initially, the membrane area and the draw solution pressure were
145 assumed and the PRO permeate flow rate, Q_{p1} , was estimated by the following
146 expression [28]:

147

$$148 \quad Q_{p1} = A_{m1} * A_w \left(\frac{\pi_{Db1} * e^{-\frac{Q_{p1}A}{k}} - \pi_{Fb1} * e^{\frac{Q_{p1}K}{A}}}{1 + \frac{B}{Q_{p1}} \left(e^{\frac{Q_{p1}K}{A}} - e^{-\frac{Q_{p1}A}{k}} \right)} - \Delta P \right) \quad [1]$$

149

150 where, Q_{p1} is the permeate flow rate (in m³/h), π_{Db1} and π_{Fb1} are the osmotic
151 pressures, respectively, of the bulk draw and bulk feed solution (in bar), k is the
152 mass transfer coefficient (in m/s), A_{m1} is the PRO membrane area (m²), A_w is
153 water permeability coefficient (in L/m²h bar), ΔP is the hydraulic pressure across
154 the PRO membrane (in bar), K is the solute resistivity for diffusion within the
155 porous support layer (in s/m), and B is the solute permeability coefficient (in m/h).
156 PRO membrane rejection rate to monovalent ions is more than 90% which
157 reduces solute transport across the membrane [22]. Equation 1 estimates water
158 flux when the draw solution is facing the membrane active layer (DS-AL) to
159 reduce the effect of internal concentration polarization and salt accumulation in
160 the membrane porous layer. Furthermore, π_{Fb1} was assumed zero because the
161 feed solution in the CLPRO process is a distilled water; i.e. $\pi_{Fb1} \ll \pi_{Db1}$. It was
162 also assumed that the operating hydraulic pressure was the average osmotic
163 pressure between π_{Fb1} and π_{Db1} , hence π_{Db1} was calculated from the following
164 equation [21]:

165

$$166 \quad \pi_{Db1} = 2 * \Delta P + \pi_{Fb1} \quad [2]$$

167

168 Water flux, J_{w1} (in L/m²h), is a function of the permeate flow and the membrane
169 area; i.e. $J_{w1} = Q_{p1}/A_m$. Van't Hoff equation was used for estimating the osmotic
170 pressure of the bulk draw solution [29]:

171

$$172 \quad \pi_{Dbl} = 1.12(273 + T) \sum m_n \quad [3]$$

173

174 where, T is feed temperature (in Kelvin), m_n is the molar concentration of n^{th} ion
175 species. It should be mentioned that NaCl was proposed as the DS of CLPRO
176 process in this study. Equation 3 can be re-arranged to estimate π_{Dbl} in mg/L as
177 the following equation:
178

$$179 \quad \pi_{Dbl} = \frac{C_{Nab} * 1.12 * T}{Mw_{Na} * 14.5} + \frac{C_{Clb} * 1.12 * T}{Mw_{Cl} * 14.5} \quad [4]$$

180

$$181 \quad C_{Clb} = \frac{Mw_{Cl}}{Mw_{Na}} C_{Nab} = 1.54 C_{Nab} \quad [5]$$

182

$$183 \quad C_{Nab} = \frac{\pi_{Dbl}}{\left(\frac{1.12T}{Mw_{Na} * 14.5}\right) + \left(\frac{1.12 * 1.54 * T}{Mw_{Cl} * 14.5}\right)} \quad [6]$$

184

185 where, C_{Nab} is the bulk concentration of Na ions (in mg/L), Mw_{Na} and Mw_{Cl} are
186 the molecular weight of Na and Cl ions (in mg/M), **respectively**, and C_{Clb} is the
187 bulk concentration of Cl ions (in mg/L).
188

189 On the other hand, the inlet concentration of **the** draw solution, C_{Di1} , was
190 estimated from **the** mass and flow balance equation in the draw solution side of
191 the membrane:
192

192

$$193 \quad C_{Di1} * Q_{Di1} + C_{P1} * Q_{P1} = C_{Do1} * Q_{Do1} \quad [7]$$

194

195

$$196 \quad C_{Do1} = 2 * C_{Dbl} - C_{Di1} \quad [8]$$

197

$$198 \quad C_{Dbl} = \frac{C_{Di1} + C_{Do1}}{2} \quad [9]$$

199

200

201 where C_{P1} is the permeate concentration (in mg/L). Assuming that C_{P1} is
202 negligible, $C_{P1} \ll C_{Do1}$ and C_{Di1} , and replacing equation 8 in equation 7:
203

203

$$204 \quad C_{Di1} * Q_{Di1} = (2 * C_{Dbl} - C_{Di1}) * Q_{Do1} \quad [10]$$

205

$$206 \quad C_{Di1} = \frac{2 * C_{Dbl} * Q_{Do1}}{Q_{Di1} + Q_{Do1}} \quad [11]$$

207

208 where, C_{Do1} is the outlet concentration of the DS (in mg/L), C_{Di1} is the inlet
 209 concentration of the DS (in mg/L), Q_{Do1} is the outlet flow rate of the DS (in L/h),
 210 Q_{Di1} is the inlet flow rate of the DS (in L/h), and C_P is the permeate concentration
 211 (in mg/L). Eventually, C_{Do1} was calculated from replacing the value of C_{Di1} from
 212 equation 11 in equation 8. The power density, W_1 (in W/m^2), was calculated from
 213 equation 12 as follows:

$$214$$

$$215 \quad W_1 = J_{w1} * \Delta P \quad [12]$$

216
 217 The power generation, P_w (in kW), by the PRO process was calculated from the
 218 following equation:

$$219$$

$$220 \quad P_w = Q_{P1} * \Delta P \quad [13]$$

221
 222 Finally, the PRO recovery rate, Re_1 , was calculated from the following equation:

$$223$$

$$224 \quad Re_1 = \frac{Q_{P1}}{Q_{F1}} \quad [14]$$

225
 226 where, Q_{F1} is the feed flow rate (in L/h).

227
 228 In the case of the dual stage, the diluted DS from the first stage of the DSPRO
 229 process is divided into two streams after leaving the membrane [see Figure 1B].
 230 The first stream goes back to a pressure exchanger to pressurize the DS. The
 231 second stream, with a volume equals to Q_{P1} , will be the draw solution of the
 232 second stage of the DSPRO process [Figure 2B]. This means that the flow rate of
 233 the DS in the second stage is equal to Q_{P1} . Furthermore, the hydraulic pressure
 234 of the first stage is equal to that of the second stage of the DSPRO process,
 235 assuming insignificant pressure losses in the first stage. The performance of the
 236 second stage of the PRO process was estimated using the following
 237 assumptions:

- 238
- 239 1. Membrane area in the second stage of the DSPRO process is calculated
 240 as the ratio of osmotic pressure driving force of the second stage to that of
 241 the first stage multiplied by A_{m1} ; i.e. $A_{m2} = A_{m1}(\Delta\pi_2 / \Delta\pi_1)$.
- 242 2. Osmotic pressure of the DS in the second stage is equal to the osmotic
 243 pressure of the diluted DS from the first stage since the diluted DS from
 244 the first stage is the DS of the second stage of the DSPRO process.
- 245 3. The osmotic pressure of FS is negligible (distilled water).

246
 247 The membrane flux in the second stage of the DSPRO process, J_{w2} , could be
 248 initially estimated from the solution diffusion model:

$$249$$

$$250 \quad J_{w2} = A_w(\Delta\pi - \Delta P) \quad [15]$$

251

252 where, A_w is the water permeability coefficient (in L/m²h.bar), $\Delta\pi$ is the osmotic
 253 pressure gradient (in bar), and ΔP is the hydraulic pressure difference (in bar).
 254 Likewise, the permeate flow rate in the second stage of the PRO process, Q_{P2} ,
 255 was calculated as:

$$256 \quad 257 \quad Q_{P2} = J_{w2} * A_{m2} \quad [16]$$

258 where A_{m2} is the membrane area in the second stage of the DSPRO process (in
 259 m²). Noting that, Q_{Do2} is the sum of Q_{Di2} and Q_{P2} . Assuming $C_{P2} \ll C_{Di2}$, the
 260 outlet concentration of the draw solution, C_{Do2} , was calculated from the
 261 concentration and mass balance on the DS side of the second stage of the
 262 DSPRO membrane:
 263

$$264 \quad 265 \quad C_{Do2} = \frac{Q_{Di2} * C_{Di2}}{Q_{Do2}} \quad [17]$$

266 where, C_{Di2} is the concentration of the DS in second stage (in mg/L). The outlet
 267 osmotic pressure of the DS, π_{Do2} (in bar), was calculated from the following
 268 equation:
 269

$$270 \quad 271 \quad \pi_{Do2} = \frac{C_{Do2} * \frac{Mw_{Na}}{Mw_{NaCl}} * 1.12 * T}{Mw_{Na} * 14.5} + \frac{C_{Do2} * \frac{Mw_{Cl}}{Mw_{NaCl}} * 1.12 * T}{Mw_{Cl} * 14.5} \quad [18]$$

272 where, Mw_{NaCl} is the molecular weight of NaCl (in mg/mol). The bulk
 273 concentration of the DS, π_{Db2} , was estimated from the following equation:
 274

$$275 \quad 276 \quad \pi_{Db2} = \frac{\pi_{Di2} + \pi_{Do2}}{2} \quad [19]$$

277 where π_{Di2} is the inlet osmotic pressure of the DS in the second stage (in bar).
 278 Then, the membrane flux of the second stage of the DSPRO, J_{w2} , was estimated
 279 from equation 20:
 280

$$281 \quad 282 \quad J_{w2} = A_w \left(\frac{\pi_{Db2} * e^{\frac{-J_{w2}}{k}} - \pi_{Fb2} * e^{J_{w2}K}}{1 + \frac{B}{J_{w2}} (e^{J_{w2}K} - e^{\frac{-J_{w2}}{k}})} - \Delta P \right) \quad [20]$$

283 In this case, the power density, W_2 (in W/m²), was estimated from equation 21:
 284

$$285 \quad 286 \quad W_2 = J_{w2} * \Delta P \quad [21]$$

287

288 The power generation of the second stage of the DSPRO, P_{w2} (in kWh), and the
 289 recovery rate, Re_2 (%), were estimated from equations 22 and 23, respectively:

291
$$P_{w2} = Q_{P2} * \Delta P \quad [22]$$

293
$$Re_2 = \frac{Q_{P2}}{Q_{F2}} \quad [23]$$

294 where, Q_{F2} is the feed flow rate of the second stage of the DSPRO process (L/h).
 295 The performance of the second stage of the PRO process was estimated by
 296 applying the iteration method described in [Figure 2].
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299

300 Figure 2: Schematic diagram that illustrates the steps for estimating the
301 performance of the second stage of the PRO process
302

303 2.2 Thermal system 304

305 The main option that has been considered for regeneration of draw solution is
306 Multiple Effect Distillation (MED) which represents the most efficient evaporative
307 technology in the desalination industry [33-34]. The potential for improving its
308 energy efficiency is large, especially by increasing the operating temperature
309 over 70°C. Higher operating temperatures will result in the precipitation of
310 sparingly-soluble metal salts in the seawater. We assumed that a source of
311 waste heat is already available for the MED regeneration process.
312

313 The MED process consists in a series of under vacuum evaporators (also called
314 effects) at decreasing pressure and temperatures, in which vapour is generated
315 in one effect and condensed in the following one. The thermal energy source that
316 drives the evaporation process in all effects is the vapour generated in the
317 previous effect, except in the first one where an external heat source is required.
318 Distillate is obtained in all evaporators from the condensation of the vapour and
319 then it is directed to flash boxes in order to exploit its heat content. The remaining
320 feed water that has not been evaporated passes from one effect to other hence
321 gets more concentrated.
322

323 The MED system simulated in this work is forward-feed (see Figure 3). In this
324 design, the vapour and feed solution go in the same direction, from the highest
325 temperature effect to the lowest temperature effect. Another characteristic of this
326 design is the preheating of feed solution before the starting point of the process.
327 Shell and tube heat exchangers are used; feed solution circulates inside the
328 tubes and a small part of the vapour generated from the evaporator condenses
329 on the external surface to produce distillate and preheats the feed.
330

331 A computer model was developed to calculate the MED performance based on
332 energy and mass balances of the feed streams [35-36]. The model was validated
333 taking into account operating conditions such as Top Brine Temperature (TBT),
334 inlet salinity and recovery ratio [36]. For the current study, model operation
335 conditions were modified hence allowing for higher TBT and recovery ratios than
336 those for seawater desalination, since no fouling is expected in the process of DS
337 regeneration. The computation of model as well as the equations and the
338 considered boundary conditions are explained below.
339

Figure 3: Layout of the forward-feed MED plant considered in this work.

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There are two options for the design models of MED plants: firstly, to establish equal areas in all the effects and secondly, to consider constant temperature difference across the effects. The first option is used for constraining the size of the effects **which is desired** to decrease the capital cost of the MED. In this model, unlike that described in our previous work [36], equal area in all effects was considered. For the computation of the model, an iteration loop was implemented in the Matlab software that starts with the temperature profile and continues until a convergence criterion is achieved. The convergence criterion of the model should have a maximum difference in effect areas of $1 \cdot 10^{-4}$ in order to achieve a good accuracy.

The temperature profile was initially obtained considering equal temperature difference ($\Delta T_{eff,i}$) in all the effects, which was determined as the following:

$$\Delta T_{eff,i} = \frac{T_{v,1} - T_{v,N}}{N - 1} \quad [24]$$

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where N is the number of effects, $T_{v,1}$ is the vapor temperature generated in the 1st effect and $T_{v,N}$ is the vapor temperature generated in the last effect. The Top Brine Temperature (TBT) is the maximum temperature reached in the first evaporator, which corresponds to the maximum temperature of the un-evaporated brine solution through the MED ($T_{b,1}$). This temperature is higher than that of the vapour generated in the evaporator ($T_{v,1}$) due to the boiling point elevation (BPE). This parameter increases with **the increase in** the content of salts in **the treated solution**. For the rest of evaporators, the brine temperature

366 was also determined by the temperature of vapour produced inside the
367 evaporator and the corresponding BPE.

368

369 The performance of the MED plant is evaluated by the Recovery Ratio (RR) and
370 the specific thermal consumption, S_{TC} . On one hand, the recovery ratio is the
371 ratio of the distillate product to the feed flow rate supplied:

372

$$RR = \frac{M_{prod}}{M_f} \quad [25]$$

373

374 where M_{prod} is the total distillate flow rate obtained from the MED plant.

375

376 On the other hand, the specific thermal consumption is defined as the thermal
377 energy supplied to the distillation unit for every m^3 of distillate produced:

378

$$S_{TC} = \frac{Q_{eff,1}}{M_{prod}} \quad [26]$$

379

380 The total distillate flow rate was determined as the sum of the flows leaving the
381 flash boxes (see Appendix 1):

382

$$M_{prod} = \sum_{i=2}^N M_{d,i} \quad [27]$$

383

384 The heat transfer provided to the first effect ($Q_{eff,1}$) was calculated by the energy
385 balance equation as in the following equation:

386

$$Q_{eff,1} = M_{gb,1}\lambda_{gb,1} + M_f C_p (T_{b,1} - T_f) = M_s \lambda_s \quad [28]$$

387

388 where T_f is the temperature of feed water sprayed in the first effect of MED, M_s is
389 the mass flow rate of low pressure steam and λ_s is the change in enthalpy related
390 to the vapour condensation.

391

392 The model was run considering the salinity and feed solution flow rate to the
393 MED plant and the recovery ratio as inputs. The first two are given by the
394 characteristics of the DS as it exits the PRO, and the third is the required
395 concentration for the regeneration. The model results give first the number of
396 effects (N) and the TBT that keep the temperature difference between the MED
397 effects ($\Delta T_{eff,i}$) in the range of 2-3 °C, which is the usual driving force used in
398 MED plants to achieve good thermal efficiencies. Then, it gives the specific
399 thermal energy consumption, the area of the evaporators and the temperature
400 profile through the evaporators.

401

402 The following assumptions were considered in the model:

- 403
- 404 - Temperature difference of cooling water between the inlet ($T_{cw,in}$) and the
- 405 outlet ($T_{cw,out}$) through the end condenser was 7.3 °C
- 406 - Cooling water inlet temperature ($T_{cw,in}$) was 25 °C
- 407 - The temperature difference between the feed solution (T_f) and the vapour
- 408 generated inside 1st effect ($T_{v,1}$) was 3 °C.
- 409 - The initial (before the iteration loop) temperature difference between the
- 410 low pressure steam (T_s) and the vapour in the 1st effect ($T_{v,1}$) was
- 411 established as 4 °C. Then, it changed once and the new temperature
- 412 profile was generated by the equal effect areas iteration loop.

413 3. Results and discussion

414 3.1 Model Calibration

415

416 The PRO model was calibrated using experimental data [12]. The **membrane**

417 **flux, J_w , and the power density, W , were calculated and compared with the**

418 **experimental results [22], using draw solution pressures close to the optimum**

419 **value of $\Delta P = \Delta\pi / 2$. In order to evaluate the impact of the draw solution pressure**

420 **on the accuracy of the PRO model, a wide range of hydraulic pressures was**

421 **used for the calibration of the PRO model in the current study. Table 1 shows the**

422 **testing parameters for calibrating the PRO model using a cellulose triacetate FO**

423 **membrane manufactured by Hydration Technology Innovations, USA [22]. It was**

424 **assumed that the same type of PRO membrane was used in the first and the**

425 **second stage of the DSPRO process.**

426

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429

430 Table 1: PRO model testing parameters

Parameter	k (m/h)	K (h/m)	A_w (m/h.bar)	B (m/h)
Value	0.306	115-125	$6.7 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$4 \cdot 10^{-4}$

431

432 J_w and W are the key performance parameters of the PRO process; these

433 parameters were calculated and compared with the experimental results [22].

434 The results showed that the experimental and model membrane fluxes, J_{w-exp} ,

435 and J_{w-mod} respectively, were in a good agreement with each other [Table 2]. The

436 percentage difference between J_{w-exp} , and J_{w-mod} , %Diff J_w , was between 2.5%

437 and 9.8%. Apparently, using feed pressures less than $\Delta\pi / 2$ did not affect the

438 model accuracy. Table 2 also shows that the difference between experimental

439 and model power density, W_{exp} and W_{mod} respectively, were between 3.5% and

440 9.7%. Generally, the difference between model and experimental power densities

441 was less than 10%. It should be noted that the difference between the model and

442 experimental could be due to the fact that the osmotic pressures of the feed

443 solutions in the experimental work were calculated by OLI Systems Inc. (Morris

444 Plains, NJ) while the osmotic pressures of the feed solutions in the model were
 445 determined by Van't Hoff equation.

446

447

448 Table 2: Model and experimental data of membrane flux and power density

449 * draw solution pressure $\Delta\pi/2$

Draw TDS (g/L)	Feed TDS (g/L)	Pressure (bar)	$J_{w\text{-exp}}$ (L/m ² h)	$J_{w\text{-mod}}$ (L/m ² h)	% Diff. J_w	W_{exp} (W/m ²)	W_{mod} (W/m ²)	% Diff. W
35*	0	13	7.9	7.7	2.5%	2.9	2.8	3.5%
	2.5	12	6.8	6.2	8.8%	2.3	2.1	8.7%
	5	11	5.6	5.1	8.9%	1.7	1.55	8.8%
60*	0	24	12.4	12	3.5%	8.3	8.0	3.6%
	2.5	23	10.1	9.5	5.9%	6.5	6.1	6.1%
	5	22.5	8.5	7.8	8.2%	5.3	4.9	7.5%
35	0	10	10.1	9.4	6.9%	2.8	2.6	7.1%
	2.5	10	7.2	6.7	7.0%	2.0	1.85	7.5%
	5	10	5.5	5.1	7.2%	1.6	1.4	6.7%
60	0	15	15.8	15	5.0%	6.8	6.3	7.3%
	2.5	15	12.2	11	9.8%	5.0	4.6	8.8%
	5	15	9.6	8.9	7.2%	4.1	3.7	9.7%

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453 3.2 Single and dual PRO system

454

455 The PRO process optimization was performed taking into account the impact of
 456 the membrane area, draw solution pressure, and DS flow rate. The performance
 457 of single and dual stage CLPRO was evaluated for comparison purposes. The
 458 effect of changing the membrane area on the performance of a single and dual
 459 stage CLPRO process is illustrated in [Figure 4]. The applied draw solution
 460 pressure was 16 bar and the draw and feed solutions flow rates in the first stage
 461 of the PRO process were 5000 L/h. PRO mode membrane orientation was
 462 selected because of the higher PRO performance [21, 27]. For the single stage
 463 CLPRO, the increase of the membrane area resulted in a minor increase in the
 464 water flux of the first stage, J_{w1} . This was accomplished by increasing the inlet
 465 concentration of DS, C_{Di1} , and the osmotic pressure, π_{Di1} of the first stage [Figure
 466 4a and 4b]. J_{w1} increased from 11.2 L/m²h to 11.6 L/m²h as membrane area
 467 increased from 200 m² to 300 m², respectively, because of the larger permeate
 468 flow. The corresponding inlet DS concentrations, C_{Di1} , were 0.86 mol/L and 0.92

469 mol/L, respectively. Practically, the modulus of external CP (ECP), $e^{\frac{-J_w}{k}}$, on the
 470 DS side of the membrane approaches a unity at negligible ECP. The results

471 show [Figure 4c] that $e^{\frac{-J_w}{k}}$ decreased slightly below a unity with the increase in
472 the membrane area indicating a higher ECP effect. Therefore, C_{Di1} was slightly
473 increased with the increase of membrane area in order to maintain J_{w1} [Figure 4a
474 and 4b].

475
476 For a DSPRO process, the high membrane flux in the first stage increased the
477 dilution of DS which in turn affected the water flux in the second stage of the
478 DSPRO, J_{w2} [Figure 4a]. Simulation results show that J_{w2} decreased from 5.0
479 L/m²h to 4.0 L/m²h due to the increase of first stage membrane area, A_{m1} , from
480 200 m² to 300 m². This was attributed to the lower osmotic pressure across the
481 PRO membrane. The osmotic pressure of the DS in the second stage, π_{Di2} ,
482 decreased from 26 bar to 23.7 bar whereas C_{Di2} decreased from 0.58 mol/L to
483 0.52 mol/L as A_{m1} increased from 200 m² to 300 m², respectively [Figure 4a and
484 4b]. Furthermore, simulation results revealed that $e^{\frac{-J_w}{k}}$ of the second stage of the
485 DSPRO process increased from 0.98 to 0.99 with the increase in the membrane
486 area, which was an indicative to the lower CP effect. In effect, the decrease of
487 J_{w2} resulted in a lower dilutive ECP at the DS side of the second stage of the
488 CLPRO process.

489
490 Recovery rates of the first and second stage of the CLPRO process are
491 illustrated in [Figure 4d]. Results reveal that the recovery rates of the first and the
492 second stage of the DSPRO, Re_1 and Re_2 , increased with the increase in the
493 A_{m1} . In this way, Re_1 was 45% at 200 m² membrane area and increased to 70%
494 at 300 m², whereas Re_2 increased from 27% to 51% as A_{m1} increased from 200
495 m² to 300 m². The total recovery rate of the DSPRO, Re_{-tot} , was 60% at 200 m²
496 and increased to 85% at 300 m². Furthermore, the power density of the first and
497 second stage, W_1 and W_2 respectively, were estimated and illustrated in [Figure
498 4e]. Simulation results revealed that W_1 increased from 6 W/m² to 6.5 W/m² as
499 A_{m1} increased from 200 m² to 300 m², whereas W_2 decreased from 2.8 W/m² to
500 2.3 W/m² as A_{m1} increased from 200 m² to 300 m² [Figure 4e]. The increase and
501 decrease, respectively, of W_1 and W_2 , reflected the increase and decrease of J_{w1}
502 and J_{w2} , respectively. The higher the water flux the higher the power density
503 produced by the PRO membrane. Finally, results show that W_2 was 45% of W_1
504 at 200 m² and decreased to 35% of W_1 at 300 m². For the rest of this study, A_{m1}
505 was assumed 300 m² because of the high PRO performance and power density,
506 especially in the first stage; i.e. ($W_1 \sim 3W_2$).

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 523 **Figure 4:** Impact of membrane area on single and dual stage PRO process a)
 524 impact on the **water** flux and DS concentration b) effect of inlet and outlet
 525 concentration of DS of single and dual stage CLPRO c) effect on dilutive
 526 concentration polarization d) effect on recovery rate of single and dual stage
 527 CLPRO e) effect on power density

528
 529 The effect of hydraulic pressure, P , on the performance of the first and second
 530 stages of the DSPRO **process** is illustrated in [Figure 5]. The performance of the
 531 CLPRO process was **modelled for a membrane area of 300 m² and 5000L/h for**
 532 Q_{Di1} and Q_{Fi1} . **Water** flux of the first stage of the DSPRO process, J_{w1} , increased
 533 from 7.2 L/m²h to 11.6 L/m²h as **draw solution** pressure increased from 10 bar to
 534 16 bar, respectively [Figure 5a]. This was due to the increase of **the** inlet
 535 concentration of DS, C_{Di1} , and the osmotic pressure, π_{Di1} , of the first stage of the
 536 DSPRO process. For example, C_{Di1} increased from 0.5 mol/L to 0.9 mol/L as the
 537 **draw solution** pressure increased from 10 bar to 16 bar; the corresponding π_{Di1}
 538 was 24 bar and 40 bar, respectively [Figure 5b]. For a PRO process operating at
 539 maximum power density, **the draw solution** pressure increased with the **increase**
 540 **in the** osmotic pressure of the salinity gradient resource. In effect, the increase of
 541 C_{Di1} was essential to provide a sufficient driving force for **the increase of** J_{w1} .
 542 Furthermore, the effect of the draw solution pressure on the ECP of the first

543 stage was illustrated in [Figure 5c]. $e^{\frac{-J_w}{k}}$ function deviated away from a unity with
 544 **the increase in the draw solution** pressure, which indicated **a** high ECP effect.

545
 546 For the second stage of the DSPRO **process**, increasing **the draw solution**
 547 pressure from 10 bar to 16 bar resulted in a slight increase of J_{w2} from 3.2 L/m²h

548 to 4.1 L/m²h. This was attributed to the increase of C_{Di2} and π_{Di2} , which resulted
 549 in a higher J_{w2} [Figures 5a and 5b]. Furthermore, $e^{\frac{-J_w}{k}}$ was decreased slightly
 550 below a unity as an indicative of the higher ECP effect on the DS side, which was
 551 caused by the high J_{w2} [Figure 5c]. The results also show that the recovery rate of
 552 first and second stage, Re_1 and Re_2 respectively, increased with the increase of
 553 the draw solution pressure from 10 bar to 16 bar. The total recovery rate of the
 554 DSPRO, i.e. the sum of Re_1 and Re_2 , increased from 58% to 85% due to the
 555 increase of draw solution pressure from 10 bar to 16 bar. Regarding PRO power
 556 density, the results are shown in [Figure 5e]. W_1 increased about 2.5 times, from
 557 2.5 W/m² to 6.46 W/m², due to the draw solution pressure increase from 10 bar
 558 to 16 bar whereas W_2 was doubled, from 1.1 W/m² to 2.3 W/m², due to the
 559 increase of draw solution pressure from 10 bar to 16 bar. In general, W_2 was
 560 about 45% and 35% of W_1 at draw solution pressures 10 bar and 16 bar,
 561 respectively. The results show that the performance of the DSPRO process was
 562 higher at a draw solution pressure of 16 bar and a A_{m1} of 300 m².
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Figure 5: Impact of draw solution pressure on the single and DSPRO performance a) effect on the water flux and draw solution concentration b) effect of inlet and outlet concentration of DS of single and dual stage CLPRO c) effect on dilutive concentration polarization d) effect on the recovery rate of single and dual stage CLPRO e) effect on power density

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The effect of the DS flow rate on the performance of CLPRO process was evaluated at a draw solution pressure of 16 bar and a membrane area of 300 m² [Figure 6]. The simulation results revealed that the J_{w1} remained constant, about 11.6 L/m²h, despite the increase in the DS flow rate from 2000 L/h to 5000 L/h [Figure 6a]. Previous studies demonstrated that the water flux increases with the increase of the DS flow rate, Q_{Di1} , due to the higher bulk osmotic pressure of the DS [30, 37]. At the present study, C_{Di1} and π_{Di1} decreased with the increase in the Q_{Di1} ; C_{Di1} and π_{Di1} were decreased to maintain a constant J_{w1} across the PRO membrane [Figure 6a and 6b]. As such, the concentration of draw solution can be decreased at high flow rates; this operating condition would reduce the effect of CP but on the expense of slightly higher pumping energy.

For the second stage, the increase of Q_{Di1} resulted in an increase of J_{w2} [Figure 6a]. This was attributed to the increase of the concentration and osmotic pressure of the DS in the second stage of DSPRO [Figure 6b]. J_{w2} was 1.6 L/m²h and 4.2 L/m²h at 2500 L/h and 5000 L/h Q_{Di1} respectively; the corresponding C_{Di2} for 2500 L/h and 5000 L/h Q_{Di1} was 0.42 mol/L and 0.52 mol/L, respectively

[Figure 6b]. $e^{-\frac{J_w}{k}}$ of the first stage of the DSPRO remained unaffected by Q_{Di1} change indicating a constant ECP, whereas J_{w2} increased with the increase of

Q_{Di1} and it resulted in a higher $e^{-\frac{J_w}{k}}$ effect at 5000 L/h Q_{Di1} [Figure 6c]. For the second stage of the DSPRO process, the outlet concentration of DS, C_{Do2} , increased from 0.39 mol/L to 0.42 mol/L due to the increase of Q_{Di1} from 2500 L/h to 5000 L/h [Figure 6b].

For the first stage, Re_1 remained constant at 70% with the increase in Q_{Di1} [Figure 6d]. However, the recovery rate of the second stage, Re_2 , increased from 14% to 51% as a result of the increase in Q_{Di1} from 2500 L/h to 5000 L/h [Figure 6d]. This was attributed to the higher permeation flow in the second stage of the DSPRO. Re_{-tot} of the DSPRO process also increased with the increase of Q_{Di1} and it reached 85% at a Q_{Di1} of 4500 L/h. Finally, the power density of the first and second stage of the DSPRO process is illustrated in [Figure 6e]. W_1 was unaffected by the variation of Q_{Di1} from 2500 L/m² to 5000 L/m². On the contrary, W_2 increased from 0.9 W/m² to 2.3 W/m² due to the increase in Q_{Di1} from 2500 L/m² to 5000 L/m². W_2 was about 20% to 70% of W_1 at 2500 L/m² and 5000 L/m² Q_{Di1} respectively. As such, W_2 was almost negligible at a Q_{Di1} of 2000 L/m². This suggests that reducing Q_{Di1} can significantly affect the performance of the second stage of the CLPRO process and hence it should be avoided. As such, a Q_{Di1} of 5000 L/m² was selected due to the higher performance of the DSPRO process.

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 637 **Figure 6:** Impact of draw solution flow rate on the performance of single and dual
 638 stage PRO process a) effect on the **water** flux and DS concentration b) effect of
 639 inlet and outlet concentration of DS of single and dual stage CLPRO c) effect on
 640 dilutive concentration polarization d) recovery rate effect on single and dual stage
 641 CLPRO e) effect on power density

642
 643 The results showed that dual stage CLPRO performed better than the single
 644 stage CLPRO at all operating conditions. But it should be observed that the draw
 645 solution pressure and the DS flow rate were the most influential parameters in
 646 the first and second stage of the DSPRO, respectively, whereas the membrane
 647 area had low impact on the process performance. In practical terms, the pressure
 648 of the draw solution would be fixed at $\Delta\pi/2$ in order to increase the power
 649 generation of the first stage while the flow rate of the DS should be increased to
 650 enhance the performance of the second stage of the DSPRO process.
 651 Furthermore, the concentration of draw solution can be decreased at high draw
 652 solution flow rates. The percentage of W_1 and W_2 variation with the membrane
 653 area, draw solution pressure and DS flow rate are presented in Table 3. The
 654 values shown in column 6 and 7 were calculated as the percentage difference
 655 with the upper value of each stage. In general, the draw solution pressure is the
 656 most influential parameter in the first stage followed by draw solution flow rate
 657 and membrane area, respectively. For example, 61% increase in W_1 was
 658 achieved due to the increase of draw solution pressure from 10 bar to 16 bar.
 659 However, the concentration of draw solution should be increased at high draw
 660 solution pressures to maintain enough osmotic potential across the membrane.
 661 For the second stage of the DSPRO, DS flow rate was the most influential
 662 parameter followed by the draw solution pressure and membrane area,

663 respectively. About the 61% increase of W_2 occurred due to the increase of the
 664 DS flow rate from 2500 L/h to 5000 L/h.

665

666 Also, the simulation results showed that W_1 was 2 to 3 times more than W_2
 667 indicating that the DSPRO efficiency is mainly based on the performance of the
 668 first stage of the DSPRO. These model results show the influence of membrane
 669 area, draw solution pressure and draw solution flow rate on the power density of
 670 the CLPRO process, thus they can be used in the design of the single and dual
 671 stage CLPRO plant and the system optimization to reduce the capital and
 672 operating costs.

673

674 Table 3: Impact of operating parameters on the inlet concentration of draw
 675 solution to the single and dual stage CLPRO process and power density of single
 676 and dual stage CLPRO process

Parameter	C_{Di1} (mol/L)	C_{Di2} (mol/L)	W_1 (W/m ²)	W_2 (W/m ²)	% Diff W_1 stage 1	% Diff W_2 stage 2
A (m ²)						
200	0.84	0.58	6.20	2.84	-3.9%	0.0%
220	0.85	0.57	6.27	2.74	-2.9%	3.7%
240	0.86	0.56	6.33	2.63	-2.0%	7.5%
260	0.87	0.54	6.38	2.52	-1.2%	11.3%
280	0.88	0.53	6.42	2.42	-0.6%	15.1%
300	0.89	0.52	6.46	2.31	0.0%	18.9%
P (bar)						
10	0.52	0.36	2.52	1.13	-61.0%	-50.8%
11	0.58	0.39	3.05	1.33	-52.7%	-42.6%
12	0.64	0.42	3.63	1.52	-43.8%	-34.1%
13	0.70	0.45	4.26	1.72	-34.0%	-25.6%
14	0.76	0.47	4.94	1.92	-23.4%	-17.0%
15	0.83	0.50	5.67	2.11	-12.1%	-8.4%
16	0.89	0.52	6.46	2.31	0.0%	0.0%
Q_{Di1} (L/h)						
2500	1.00	0.42	6.46	0.90	-	-60.9%
3000	0.97	0.45	6.46	1.34	-	-42.0%
3500	0.94	0.47	6.46	1.67	-	-27.6%
4000	0.92	0.49	6.46	1.93	-	-16.4%
4500	0.90	0.51	6.46	2.14	-	-7.4%
5000	0.89	0.52	6.46	2.31	-	0.0%

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680 3.3 MED regeneration system

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682 The MED model described in Section 2.3 was considered for the draw solution
 683 regeneration. The effect of PRO membrane area on the MED performance was
 684 evaluated using 16 bar as the draw solution pressure and a draw solution flow
 685 rate of 5000 L/h [Figure 7]. The recovery rate of the MED process increased
 686 with the increase of the PRO membrane area [Figure 7a]. At a membrane area of 300

687 m², the maximum recovery rate of single stage CLPRO, Re_1 , was 46.5% which is
688 8% lower than the recovery rate of the dual stage CLPRO, Re_2 . The TBT of the
689 MED plant was 73 °C at Re_1 of 46.5%, and increased to 76 °C at Re_2 of 50.2%
690 [Figure 7a]. For a single stage PRO process, TBT increased from 67 °C to 73 °C
691 due to the increase of Re_1 from 35.8% to 46.5%, respectively. For a dual stage
692 CLPRO process, TBT was 71 °C and 76 °C at Re_2 40.7% and 50.2%,
693 respectively. Therefore, the TBT for a single stage CLPRO was 4% and 6% lower
694 than that for a dual stage CLPRO process at a draw solution pressure of 10 bar
695 and 16 bar, respectively. Dual stage CLPRO process, in practice, requires higher
696 TBT than single stage PRO due to the higher recovery rates achieved by the
697 former process. The Specific Thermal Consumption (S_{TC}) represents the thermal
698 power required for saline water purification. Figure 8b shows the S_{TC} for the
699 regeneration of DS in a single and dual stage CLPRO. S_{TC} for a single stage was
700 higher than that for a dual stage CLPRO process [Figure 7b]. S_{TC} for the single
701 stage CLPRO process decreased from 67 kWh/m³ at 200 m² to 51 kWh/m³ at
702 300 m². For the dual stage CLPRO process, S_{TC} decreased from 61 kWh/m³ at
703 200 m² to 48 kWh/m³ at 300 m². The results reveal that S_{TC} for the dual stage
704 CLPRO was lower than that for the single stage. However, that was on the
705 expense of the higher heat transfer area, A_{eff} , required for the dual stage CLPRO
706 process [Figure 7b], which is disadvantageous due to the fact that the increase of
707 the A_{eff} lead to a rise in the capital cost of the MED process. Results in Table 4
708 show the number of effects of MED plant suggested for draw solution
709 regeneration. Obviously, the number of effects of the MED plant for the
710 regeneration of DS from a dual stage CLPRO was higher than that for the single
711 stage CLPRO process. This also suggests that the MED capital cost for draw
712 solution regeneration would be higher in the case of a dual stage CLPRO
713 process. P_{W-MED} represents the electric energy required for the draw solution
714 regeneration by the MED process, which is considered about 1.2 kWh/m³ [39].
715 The ratio of P_{W-PRO}/P_{W-MED} was 103% and 127% for the single and dual stage
716 CLPRO, respectively [Figure 7c]. P_{W-PRO}/P_{W-MED} ratio over hundred was an
717 indicative of a positive power generation; i.e. power generation by CLPRO is
718 higher than the power consumption for the regeneration of DS. Results show that
719 the P_{W-PRO}/P_{W-MED} ratio increased to 162% and 186% for the single and dual
720 stage CLPRO, respectively. Apparently, the energy efficiency of the dual stage
721 CLPRO was higher than that of the single stage, which will potentially pay off for
722 the higher capital cost of the dual stage CLPRO system.
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Figure 7: Impact of CLPRO membrane area on the specifications of MED thermal plant a) effect on recovery rate and TBT b) effect on specific thermal consumption and heat transfer area c) effect of membrane area on the energy efficiency

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The impact of the draw solution pressure on the performance of the MED regeneration plant was evaluated using a membrane area of 300 m² and a Q_{Di1} of 5000 L/h [Figure 8]. Re_1 and Re_2 increased with the increase in the PRO membrane area. However, Re_2 was 16% higher than Re_1 at a draw solution pressure of 10 bar. The TBT required for the DS regeneration in a dual stage CLPRO was higher than that required in a single stage CLPRO [Figure 8a]. Furthermore, at a draw solution pressure of 16 bar, Re_2 was 10% higher than Re_1 whereas the TBT required for the DS regeneration in the dual stage CLPRO was only 4% higher than that required for the DS regeneration in the single stage CLPRO. The TBT required for the regeneration of DS was 69 °C and 72 °C for the single and the dual stage CLPRO processes, respectively [Figure 8a]. These TBT's were almost within the range of operating temperatures required in the thermal energy source for commercial MED plants.

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The S_{TC} for the draw solution regeneration of the single stage CLPRO process was 77 kWh/m³ and 55 kWh/m³ at a draw solution pressure of 10 bar and 16 bar, respectively [Figure 8b]. This was higher than the S_{TC} required for the draw solution regeneration of the dual stage CLPRO process: 69 kWh/m³ and 51 kWh/m³ at 10 bar and 16 bar, respectively. Furthermore, the dual stage required slightly more A_{eff} than the single stage CLPRO process. It should be noticed that

756 the difference of A_{eff} between the single stage and the dual stage CLPRO
 757 process decreased at a draw solution pressure of 16 bar [Figure 8c]. Table 4
 758 shows the number of effects of the MED plant, in which it can be seen that
 759 between 11 and 15 effects were required for the regeneration of DS in the single
 760 stage CLPRO whereas between 12 and 18 effects were required in the MED for
 761 the regeneration of DS in the dual stage CLPRO.

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763 The results also showed a P_{W-PRO}/P_{W-MED} ratio over a hundred percent,
 764 indicating a positive power generation, i.e. power generation by the CLPRO was
 765 higher than the electric power consumption by the MED process for regenerating
 766 the DS [Figure 8c]. For the single and dual stage CLPRO, the P_{W-PRO}/P_{W-MED}
 767 ratio increased with the increase of the draw solution pressure from 10 bar to 16
 768 bar. At a draw solution pressure of 16 bar, the ratio of P_{W-PRO}/P_{W-MED} was 132%
 769 and 157% for the single and dual stage CLPRO process, respectively. Indeed,
 770 the dual stage CLPRO process was more energy efficient than the single stage
 771 process. It should be noted that the difference of the P_{W-PRO}/P_{W-MED} ratio between
 772 the single and dual stage CLPRO process increased with the increase in the feed
 773 pressure. Thus, the efficiency of the dual stage CLPRO process increases with
 774 the increase in the feed pressure.

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Figure 8: Impact of CLPRO draw solution pressure on the specifications of MED thermal plant a) effect on recovery rate and TBT b) effect on specific thermal consumption and heat transfer area c) effect of membrane area on the energy efficiency

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788 **Figure 9** shows the impact of the draw solution flow rate, Q_{Di1} , on the
789 performance of **the CLPRO process** at a **draw solution** pressure of 16 bar and a
790 PRO membrane area of 300 m². Re_1 and Re_2 decreased with the increase in Q_{Di1}
791 from 2500 L/h to 5000 L/h. However, Re_2 was always higher than Re_1 but the
792 difference between Re_1 and Re_2 increased with the increase in Q_{Di1} [**Figure 9a**].
793 Furthermore, the TBT of the MED regeneration process for the single stage
794 CLPRO process was unaffected by the increase of Q_{Di1} . However, this was on
795 the expense of higher S_{TC} at high Q_{Di1} [Table 4]. In the case of **the dual stage**
796 **CLPRO process**, the TBT of the MED was very sensitive to the change of Q_{Di1} . In
797 general, the TBT of **the MED unit** treating a diluted draw solution from a single
798 stage CLPRO process was lower than that from a dual stage CLPRO **process**. At
799 a **draw solution** pressure of 16 bar, the TBT of **the MED** plant was 72 °C and 76
800 °C for a single and dual stage CLPRO, respectively. These TBTs were slightly
801 higher than that normally used in the commercial MED plants. The results also
802 **revealed** that the S_{TC} for the DS regeneration from the single stage CLPRO
803 process was higher than that for the DS regeneration from the dual stage CLPRO
804 [**Figure 9b**]. However, A_{eff} of the MED was higher for the dual stage CLPRO
805 [**Figure 9b**] but the difference in A_{eff} between the single stage and the dual stage
806 CLPRO process slightly decreased with the increase in the Q_{Di1} . Thus, applying
807 high draw solution flow rates would decrease the capital cost of the MED plant.

808

809 The ratio of P_{W-PRO}/P_{W-MED} for a single stage CLPRO process remained constant
810 at 161% despite the increase of Q_{Di1} [**Figure 9c**]. For the dual stage CLPRO, the
811 ratio of P_{W-PRO}/P_{W-MED} was 171% at 2500 L/h but increased to 195% at 5000 L/h
812 Q_{Di1} . This suggests that dual stage CLPRO process was more energy efficient
813 than the single stage CLPRO process especially at higher Q_{Di1} . At 5000 L/h Q_{Di1} ,
814 the ratio of P_{W-PRO}/P_{W-MED} for the dual stage CLPRO was 21% higher than that for
815 the single stage CLPRO process. MED regeneration of the DS resulted in a
816 positive PRO power generation assuming that the power consumption in the
817 MED process was mainly electrical whereas thermal energy provided by a source
818 of waste heat.

819

820 The dual stage CLPRO process is more energy efficient than the single stage
821 CLPRO but it requires higher TBT and heat transfer area for the regeneration of
822 the draw solution by the MED process. **The range of TBT for the regeneration of**
823 **DS was between 67 °C and 75 °C for the dual stage CLPRO which will not affect**
824 **the operation cost of the MED plant if a free source of waste heat is available.**
825 **Interestingly, the S_{TC} of MED for treatment of DS from the dual stage CLPRO**
826 **was lower than that of MED for treatment of DS from the single stage CLPRO.**
827 **This emphasizes the superiority of dual stage CLPRO process over the single**
828 **stage CLPRO process. The results suggest that dual stage CLPRO coupling with**
829 **the MED process can be a viable option for power generation from a salinity**
830 **gradient resource. The system can be also used for energy storage. In this case,**
831 **a source of thermal energy would be applied for the regeneration of draw and**

832 feed solution by the MED process. This energy can be recovered later on by
833 pairing the draw and feed solutions in the PRO process for power generation.
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Figure 9: Effect of CLPRO DS flow rate on the specifications of MED thermal plant a) effect on recovery rate and TBT b) effect on specific thermal consumption and heat transfer area c) effect of membrane area on the energy efficiency of single and dual stage CLPRO

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Table 4: Impact of CLPRO operating parameters on the specific thermal consumption and number of effects of the single and dual stage CLPRO process

Parameter	Single stage CLPRO		Dual stage CLPRO	
	S_{TC} kWh/m ³	No. Effects	S_{TC} kWh/m ³	No. Effects
A (m ²)				
200	66.99	13	61.2	14
220	62.73	14	57.72	15
240	59.17	15	54.74	16
260	56	16	52.08	17
280	53.29	17	49.81	18
300	50.85	18	47.76	19
P bar				
10	76.7	11	69.29	12
11	71.41	12	64.99	13
12	67.14	13	61.31	14
13	63.37	14	58.16	15
14	60.11	15	55.4	16
15	57.22	16	52.98	17
16	54.74	15	50.87	18
Q_{D1} L/h				
3000	58.16	14	55.08	15
3500	58.99	14	55.42	15
4000	59.59	14	55.79	15
4500	60.28	14	56.14	15
5000	60.83	14	56.47	15

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4. Conclusions

855 CLPRO process was suggested for power generation using single and dual stage
856 configuration. A computer model was developed to predict the performance of
857 the DSPRO process. The effect of membrane area, DS flow rate and draw
858 solution pressure on the performance of the DSPRO process was investigated.
859 Simulation results revealed that the effect of the draw solution pressure on the
860 performance of the first stage was higher than the effect of other parameters. On
861 the other hand, the DS flow rate was the most influential parameters in the
862 second stage. As such, the draw solution pressure needs to be optimized during
863 the design of a DSPRO process.

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Regardless the regeneration process, the dual stage CLPRO process
outperformed the single stage CLPRO process, which underlined the superiority
of the former system for power generation by osmotic energy. The power density
of the DSPRO process was 43% more than that generated by the single stage
CLPRO process. Furthermore, the simulation results showed that the MED

870 system requires about 3 °C higher temperature for the regeneration of the draw
 871 solution in the dual stage CLPRO process. This thermal process would be
 872 feasible as a heat engine when an affordable source of low grade heat is
 873 available. In terms of capital costs, it would be slightly higher in the case of dual
 874 stage CLPRO due to the larger membrane and heat transfer areas of the PRO-
 875 MED system but capital cost increase will be paid off over time due to the higher
 876 energy efficiency of the dual stage CLPRO process.

877

878 **Appendix 1: Equations of the MED model.**

879

880 The MED model is described elsewhere [36-37], but some equations have been
 881 particularized for this study.

882

883 The area of each evaporator ($A_{eff,i}$) was determined by calculating the
 884 temperature difference between the un-evaporated brine in the effect i ($T_{b,i}$) and
 885 the vapour that comes from the preceding effect and enters in the effect i ($T_{v,i-1}$),
 886 and the heat transfer rate provided to the effect i ($Q_{eff,i}$). Likewise, rate of heat
 887 transfer is equal to the change in enthalpy related to the condensation of the
 888 vapour coming from the previous effect and entering in the effect i ($\lambda_{v,i-1}$):

889

$$Q_{eff,i} = U_{eff,i} A_{eff,i} (T_{v,i-1} - T_{b,i}) = M_{v,i} \lambda_{v,i-1} \quad [A1]$$

890

891 where $U_{eff,i}$ is the total heat transfer coefficient, which is obtained by the
 892 correlation suggested in our previous work [37], and $M_{v,i}$ is the vapour mass flow
 893 rate going to the bundle tube of each effect, which consists of the total vapour
 894 generated by boiling of the brine ($M_{gb,i-1}$), flashing of the brine ($M_{gf,i-1}$) and
 895 flashing of the distilled water in the flash box ($M_{df,i-1}$), all of it minus the vapour
 896 consumed in the preheater ($M_{vh,i-1}$), as shown in the following equation:

897

$$M_{v,i} = (M_{gb,i-1} + M_{gf,i-1} + M_{df,i-1}) - M_{vh,i-1} \quad [A2]$$

898

899 Each mass flow rate of the previous equation (M), is determined by energy
 900 balances in the effects, the preheaters and the flash boxes.

901

902 The vapour consumed in the preheater, $M_{vh,i}$, is condensed releasing latent heat
 903 $\lambda_{vh,i}$ (at a temperature $T_{v,i}$) which is utilized to heat the feed water flowing through
 904 the preheaters tube bundle:

905

$$M_{vh,i} \lambda_{vh,i} = M_f C_p (T_{ph,i} - T_{ph,i+1}) \quad [A3]$$

906

907 where $T_{ph,i}$ is the feed water temperature in the bundle tube of a preheater i , and
 908 M_f is defined as the mass flow rate of feed solution sprayed in 1st effect.

909

910 In the case of preheaters, it was assumed an equal temperature difference
 911 between preheaters ($\Delta T_{preh,i}$), which is determined from the following expression:
 912

$$\Delta T_{preh,i} = \frac{T_{ph,1} - T_{ph,Nph}}{N_{ph}} \quad [A4]$$

913
 914 where N_{ph} is the number of preheaters, which is considered equal to $N - 1$.
 915

916 Additionally, mass flow rate of the vapour generated in each evaporator is
 917 obtained by the following energy balance:
 918

$$M_{gb,i} \lambda_{gb,i} = M_{v,i} \lambda_{v,i-1} + M_{db,i} C_p (T_{db,i} - T_{b,i}) \quad [A5]$$

919
 920 $M_{db,i}$ is the mass flow rate of the brine solution after flashing once it enters the
 921 effect (at a higher pressure than that one inside the effect), $\lambda_{gb,i}$ is the latent heat
 922 of vaporization at $T_{v,i}$ and $T_{db,i}$ is the un-evaporated brine temperature after
 923 flashing. $M_{db,i}$ was determined by the following mass balance:
 924

$$M_{db,i} = M_{b,i-1} - M_{gf,i} \quad [A6]$$

925
 926 The mass flow rate of the flashing brine was determined by an energy balance:
 927

$$M_{gf,i} \lambda_{gf,i} = M_{b,i-1} C_p (T_{b,i-1} - T_{db,i}) \quad [A7]$$

928
 929 where $\lambda_{gf,i}$ is the vaporization latent heat at $T_{v,i}$.
 930

931 Both mass flow rates (M_{gf} , M_{db}) were considered zero in the first effect, since in
 932 this case the feed solution enters at a temperature below saturation (sub-cooled);
 933 i.e. no vapour is produced by the flashing process.
 934

935 $M_{b,i}$ is the mass flow rate of the brine that leaves each effect and enters the
 936 following one and it was determined from the following equation:
 937

$$M_{b,i} = M_{db,i} - M_{gb,i} \quad [A8]$$

938
 939 Finally, the mass flow rate of the vapour produced through flashing of the
 940 distillate in each flash box was calculated by:
 941

$$M_{df,i} \lambda_{df,i} = M_{vh,i-1} C_p (T_{v,i-1} - T_{v,i}) + M_{v,i-1} C_p (T_{v,i-1} - T_{v,i}) + M_{d,i-1} C_p (T_{v,i-1} - T_{v,i}) \quad [A9]$$

942
 943 where $\lambda_{df,i}$ is the vaporization latent heat at $T_{v,i}$ and $M_{d,i}$ is the distillate mass flow
 944 rate leaving each flash box, which was determined from the following mass
 945 balance formula:

946

$$M_{d,i} = M_{v,i} + M_{vh,i-1} + M_{d,i-1} - M_{df,i} \quad [A10]$$

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950

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954

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Abbreviations:

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Abbreviation	Full Meaning
CLPRO	Closed-Loop Pressure Retarded Osmosis
MED	Multi-Effect Distillation
RO	Reverse Osmosis
PRO	Pressure Retarded Osmosis
RED	Reverse Electrodialysis
DS	Draw Solution
FS	Feed Solution
CP	Concentration Polarization
DSPRO	Dual Stage Pressure Retarded Osmosis
SSPRO	Standard Single Stage Pressure Retarded Osmosis
ERD	Energy Recovery Device
TBT	Top Brine Temperature
BPE	boiling point elevation
RR	Recovery Ratio
S _{TC}	Specific Thermal Consumption

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Nomenclature

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Nomenclature	Full Meaning
Q_p	PRO permeate flow rate (m ³ /h)
π_{Db}	osmotic pressure of the bulk draw solution (bar)
π_{Fb}	osmotic pressure of the feed draw solution (bar)
k	mass transfer coefficient (m/s)
A_m	PRO membrane area (m ²)
A_w	water permeability coefficient (L/m ² h bar)
ΔP	hydraulic pressure difference (bar)
$\Delta \pi$	osmotic pressure gradient (bar)
B	solute permeability coefficient (m/h)
K	solute resistivity for diffusion within porous support layer (s/m)
J_w	membrane flux (L/m ² h)
T	feed temperature (K)
m_n	molar concentration of n th ion species

$C_{Na,b}$	bulk concentration of Na ion (mg/L)
$C_{Cl,b}$	bulk concentration of Cl ion (mg/L)
MW_{Na}	molecular weight of Na (mg/M)
MW_{Cl}	molecular weight of Cl (mg/M)
C_{Di}	inlet concentration of draw solution (mg/L)
C_{Do}	outlet concentration of draw solution (mg/L)
Q_{Di}	inlet flow rate of draw solution (L/h)
Q_{Do}	outlet flow rate of draw solution (L/h)
C_p	permeate concentration (mg/L)
W	power density (W/m^2)
C_p	permeate concentration (mg/L)
P_w	power generation (kW)
Re	PRO recovery rate
Q_F	feed flow rate (L/h)
Q_P	permeate flow rate (L/h)
$\Delta\pi$	osmotic pressure gradient (bar)
$ES-RO$	specific power consumption of RO (kWh/m^3)
P_f	RO feed pressure (bar)
P_p	RO permeate pressure (bar)
P_{W-RO}	RO power consumption (kWh)
η	Pump efficiency
Q_{hpp}	feed flow rate of high pressure pump (m^3/h)
Q_{bp}	feed flow rate of booster pump (m^3/h)
Q_{sp}	feed flow rate of supply pump (m^3/h)
P_{bpin}	inlet pressure of booster pump (bar)
P_{hpp}	outlet pressure of high pressure pump (bar)
P_{f-hpp}	pressure of feed flow to the high pressure pump (bar)
P_{f-sp}	pressure of feed flow to supply pump (bar)
η_{hpp}	efficiency of high pressure pump
η_{bp}	efficiency of booster pump
η_{sp}	efficiency of supply pump
N	number of effects
N_{ph}	number of preheaters
$T_{v,i}$	vapor temperature generated in the i effect ($^{\circ}C$)
$T_{v,N}$	vapor temperature generated in the last effect ($^{\circ}C$)
$T_{b,1}$	brine temperature of un-evaporated solution through MED ($^{\circ}C$)
$\Delta T_{eff,i}$	temperature difference in MED effects ($^{\circ}C$)
T_f	temperature of feed water ($^{\circ}C$)
$T_{cw,in}$	cooling water inlet temperature ($^{\circ}C$)
$T_{cw,out}$	cooling water outlet temperature ($^{\circ}C$)
T_s	temperature of low pressure steam ($^{\circ}C$)
$T_{ph,i}$	feed water temperature in the bundle tube of a preheater i
$\Delta T_{preh,i}$	temperature difference between preheaters ($^{\circ}C$)
$T_{db,i}$	un-evaporated brine temperature after flashing ($^{\circ}C$)
$A_{eff,i}$	area of each effect (m^2)

$U_{eff,i}$	total heat transfer coefficient (W
$Q_{eff,i}$	heat transfer provided to the i-effect of MED
M_s	flow rate of low pressure steam mass
M_{prod}	total distillate flow rate
M_f	mass flow rate of feed solution sprayed in 1 st effect
λ_s	enthalpy change related to the vapor condensation
$\lambda_{gb,i}$	latent heat of vaporization
$M_{v,i}$	vapour mass flow rate going to the bundle tube of each effect
$M_{gb,i-1}$	vapour mass flow rate generated by boiling of the brine
$M_{gf,i-1}$	vapour mass flow rate generated by flashing of the brine
$M_{df,i-1}$	vapour mass flow rate generated by flashing of the distillate water
$M_{vh,i-1}$	vapour mass flow rate consumed in preheater
$M_{db,i}$	mass flow rate of the brine solution after flashing

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Single and Dual Stage Closed-Loop Pressure Retarded Osmosis for Power Generation: Feasibility and Performance

2

3

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10

11

Abstract

12

13

14 This work proposes an analysis of conventional (single stage) and dual stage
15 Closed-Loop Pressure Retarded Osmosis (CLPRO) for power generation from a
16 salinity gradient resource. Model calculations were performed taking into account
17 the influence of operating parameters such as the draw solution concentration,
18 membrane area, and draw solution pressure on the performance of the CLPRO
19 process. Modeling results showed that the dual stage CLPRO process
20 outperformed the conventional CLPRO process and power generation increased
21 18% by adding a second stage of PRO membrane. Multi-Effect Distillation (MED)
22 was selected for the regeneration of the draw solution taking advantage of an
23 available source of waste heat energy. The performance of MED process has
24 been assessed by investigating two key parameters: the specific thermal
25 consumption and the specific heat transfer area. The model calculations showed
26 that the power generation by the single and dual stage CLPRO was higher than
27 the electrical power consumption by the MED plant. In the case of the power
28 generation obtained by the dual stage CLPRO, it was 95% higher than the
29 electrical power consumption by the MED plant, proving the possibility of using
30 low-grade heat for producing electricity from a salinity gradient resource.

31

32 *Keywords: Pressure Retarded Osmosis, Dual Stage Pressure Retarded*
33 *Osmosis, Osmotic Power Plant, Thermal Regeneration, Dual Stage PRO*
34 *Optimization*

35

1. Introduction:

36

37
38 The application of salinity gradient resource for power generation has been
39 widely recognized as an efficient and low cost approach of renewable energy [1-
40 8]. The most common techniques for power generation from a salinity gradient
41 are the Pressure Retarded Osmosis (PRO) and Reverse Electrodialysis (RED)
42 [1-14]. PRO process has attracted a lot of attention for harvesting the energy of
43 salinity gradient because of its high efficiency and flexibility to be combined with
44 desalination technologies such as Reverse Osmosis (RO) [6, 7, 10, 12].

45 Experimental works have demonstrated the feasibility of PRO process application
46 in a small commercial power plant [15]. Closed-Loop PRO (CLPRO) has also
47 been proposed for power generation as a heat engine but only few studies have
48 been published in this field [8, 16, 17]. Previous studies focused on the
49 performance of the PRO part and no data have been provided about the
50 performance of the entire CLPRO-thermal system. Furthermore, no studies have
51 been published yet on the potential of using closed-loop dual stage PRO process
52 for power generation.

53
54 PRO process uses osmotic energy as the driving force for power generation. A
55 high osmotic pressure draw solution (DS) is fed at one side of a semipermeable
56 membrane whereas a low osmotic pressure feed solution (FS) is pumped into the
57 opposite side of the membrane to create an osmotic pressure gradient, which
58 induces fresh water transportation towards the DS [Figure 1]. Fresh water
59 transport across the membrane will convert the chemical potential into a
60 hydraulic energy. Finally, the diluted DS is depressurized by a hydroturbine for
61 power generation. Although PRO was suggested in the seventies [18], it did not
62 receive considerable attention due to the technical limitations associated with the
63 membrane permeability and rejection rate [14-19]. Recent developments in the
64 membrane manufacturing industries have brought back the strong interest in the
65 PRO concept for power generation [19-20]. New PRO membranes have high
66 water permeability and rejection rate, which revolutionized the PRO and
67 enhanced its performance [18]. Pilot plant tests using Toyobo membrane
68 demonstrated high power density of 7.7 W/m^2 [15], which was more than the
69 theoretical recommended value (5 W/m^2) for an economic PRO process [20].
70 Furthermore, previous studies have achieved power density larger than 10 W/m^2
71 using a laboratory fabricated PRO membrane and 6%-0.06% salinity gradient
72 resource [19].

73
74 One of the operating challenges for the PRO process is the selection of a
75 suitable salinity gradient resource to create a sufficient driving force across the
76 PRO membrane. A number of salinity gradients have been suggested by
77 coupling seawater or brine from a Reverse Osmosis (RO) process with
78 wastewater effluent or fresh water [14, 15, 20-22]. It is preferable applying high
79 concentration DS to obtain high membrane flux across the PRO membrane.
80 Previous works showed that Concentration Polarization (CP) across the
81 membrane increases with increasing permeation flow and reducing the efficiency
82 of PRO process [23-25]. CP is divided into dilutive and concentrative; dilutive CP
83 occurs usually on the DS side whereas the concentrative CP occurs on the FS.
84 However, using deionized water negates the effect of concentrative CP and
85 improves the performance of PRO [23].

86
87 Closed-Loop PRO (CLPRO) has been proposed as a means for salinity gradient
88 energy capture when no natural streams are available [25]. The salinity gradient
89 resource in the CLPRO process consists of a high osmotic pressure DS and
90 deionized/low concentration FS [Figure 1A]. In this case, the diluted DS goes to a

91 regeneration unit after leaving the hydroturbine system [24]. The concentrated
92 DS and fresh water are the products of the regeneration process which are
93 recycled back to the PRO membrane. Due to the high purity of draw and feed
94 solutions, CLPRO has the advantage of reducing the PRO membrane fouling,
95 and allowing the recycling and reuse of the salinity gradient resource [8].
96 Furthermore, the osmotic pressure of the CLPRO process can be flexibly
97 designed by changing the concentration and hydraulic pressure of DS. Figure 1
98 shows a schematic diagram of single and dual stage CLRPO plants which are
99 operated in a continuous mode. Practically, the feed solution would be
100 contaminated due to NaCl back diffusion from the DS. Therefore, the feed
101 solution needs purging over time whereas the concentration of DS can be
102 adjusted by adding the NaCl stock solution.

103

104 Some recent published studies have analyzed the performance of conventional
105 PRO process in the CLPRO process [25-26]. Dual stage PRO (DSPRO) process
106 has shown higher power generation potential than conventional PRO [27, 29].
107 The process has the potential of increasing the energy yield of salinity gradient
108 and reducing the membrane fouling [27, 29, 32], but no studies have investigated
109 its performance in a CLPRO system so far. The present study was focused on
110 analyzing the performance of a dual stage CLPRO process and on
111 demonstrating its advantages over the single stage CLPRO process. Also, the
112 regeneration of the draw solution by a thermal desalination process such as
113 Multi-effect distillation (MED) has been investigated. For this purpose, the use of
114 a free source of waste heat has been considered and a certain specific electricity
115 consumption of the MED system was assumed in the calculation of the net power
116 generation of the PRO process. A pre-developed computer model was applied
117 for optimizing the concentration and osmotic pressure of the DS, taking into
118 account the effect of some key operating parameters such as the draw solution
119 pressure, flow rates, and membrane area on the performance of the PRO
120 process. The PRO model was calibrated using experimental data [12] and the
121 PRO data outputs were taken as the inputs to the MED regeneration process for
122 energy calculations purposes. For the regeneration part, a computer model was
123 used in order to analyze the performance of MED system under several
124 operating conditions. The results define a baseline for the potential and feasibility
125 of CLPRO for power production.

A: Single Stage

B: Dual Stage

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127
128
129

Figure 1: Schematic diagram of closed-loop PRO system

130 2. Systems Modeling

131

132 This section describes the models used for the optimization of the PRO system
133 and the methodology used for the process simulation.

134

135 2.1 PRO system

136

137 Single and DSPRO were evaluated for a CLPRO process for power generation.
138 Figures 1A and 1B show the schematic diagram of a single and dual stage
139 CLPRO, respectively. For a single stage PRO, the membrane flux, DS
140 concentration, recovery rate and power density were optimized taking into
141 account the effect of membrane area, draw solution pressure and DS flow rate on
142 the performance of the PRO process. The following equations were applied for
143 estimating the performance and the power generation of a single stage CLPRO
144 process [23]. Initially, the membrane area and the draw solution pressure were
145 assumed and the PRO permeate flow rate, Q_{p1} , was estimated by the following
146 expression [28]:

147

$$148 \quad Q_{p1} = A_{m1} * A_w \left(\frac{\pi_{Dbl} * e^{-\frac{Q_{p1}A}{k}} - \pi_{Fbl} * e^{\frac{Q_{p1}K}{A}}}{1 + \frac{B}{Q_{p1}} \left(e^{\frac{Q_{p1}K}{A}} - e^{-\frac{Q_{p1}A}{k}} \right)} - \Delta P \right) \quad [1]$$

149

150 where, Q_{p1} is the permeate flow rate (in m³/h), π_{Dbl} and π_{Fbl} are the osmotic
151 pressures, respectively, of the bulk draw and bulk feed solution (in bar), k is the
152 mass transfer coefficient (in m/s), A_{m1} is the PRO membrane area (m²), A_w is
153 water permeability coefficient (in L/m²h bar), ΔP is the hydraulic pressure across
154 the PRO membrane (in bar), K is the solute resistivity for diffusion within the
155 porous support layer (in s/m), and B is the solute permeability coefficient (in m/h).
156 PRO membrane rejection rate to monovalent ions is more than 90% which
157 reduces solute transport across the membrane [22]. Equation 1 estimates water
158 flux when the draw solution is facing the membrane active layer (DS-AL) to
159 reduce the effect of internal concentration polarization and salt accumulation in
160 the membrane porous layer. Furthermore, π_{Fbl} was assumed zero because the
161 feed solution in the CLPRO process is a distilled water; i.e. $\pi_{Fbl} \ll \pi_{Dbl}$. It was
162 also assumed that the operating hydraulic pressure was the average osmotic
163 pressure between π_{Fbl} and π_{Dbl} , hence π_{Dbl} was calculated from the following
164 equation [21]:

165

$$166 \quad \pi_{Dbl} = 2 * \Delta P + \pi_{Fbl} \quad [2]$$

167

168 Water flux, J_{w1} (in L/m²h), is a function of the permeate flow and the membrane
169 area; i.e. $J_{w1} = Q_{p1}/A_m$. Van't Hoff equation was used for estimating the osmotic
170 pressure of the bulk draw solution [29]:

171

$$172 \quad \pi_{Dbl} = 1.12(273 + T) \sum m_n \quad [3]$$

173

174 where, T is feed temperature (in Kelvin), m_n is the molar concentration of n^{th} ion
175 species. It should be mentioned that NaCl was proposed as the DS of CLPRO
176 process in this study. Equation 3 can be re-arranged to estimate π_{Dbl} in mg/L as
177 the following equation:
178

$$179 \quad \pi_{Dbl} = \frac{C_{Nab} * 1.12 * T}{Mw_{Na} * 14.5} + \frac{C_{Clb} * 1.12 * T}{Mw_{Cl} * 14.5} \quad [4]$$

180

$$181 \quad C_{Clb} = \frac{Mw_{Cl}}{Mw_{Na}} C_{Nab} = 1.54 C_{Nab} \quad [5]$$

182

$$183 \quad C_{Nab} = \frac{\pi_{Dbl}}{\left(\frac{1.12T}{Mw_{Na} * 14.5}\right) + \left(\frac{1.12 * 1.54 * T}{Mw_{Cl} * 14.5}\right)} \quad [6]$$

184

185 where, C_{Nab} is the bulk concentration of Na ions (in mg/L), Mw_{Na} and Mw_{Cl} are
186 the molecular weight of Na and Cl ions (in mg/M), respectively, and C_{Clb} is the
187 bulk concentration of Cl ions (in mg/L).
188

189 On the other hand, the inlet concentration of the draw solution, C_{Di1} , was
190 estimated from the mass and flow balance equation in the draw solution side of
191 the membrane:
192

$$193 \quad C_{Di1} * Q_{Di1} + C_{P1} * Q_{P1} = C_{Do1} * Q_{Do1} \quad [7]$$

194

195

$$196 \quad C_{Do1} = 2 * C_{Dbl} - C_{Di1} \quad [8]$$

197

$$198 \quad C_{Dbl} = \frac{C_{Di1} + C_{Do1}}{2} \quad [9]$$

199

200

201 where C_{P1} is the permeate concentration (in mg/L). Assuming that C_{P1} is
202 negligible, $C_{P1} \ll C_{Do1}$ and C_{Di1} , and replacing equation 8 in equation 7:
203

$$204 \quad C_{Di1} * Q_{Di1} = (2 * C_{Dbl} - C_{Di1}) * Q_{Do1} \quad [10]$$

205

$$206 \quad C_{Di1} = \frac{2 * C_{Dbl} * Q_{Do1}}{Q_{Di1} + Q_{Do1}} \quad [11]$$

207

208 where, C_{Do1} is the outlet concentration of the DS (in mg/L), C_{Di1} is the inlet
 209 concentration of the DS (in mg/L), Q_{Do1} is the outlet flow rate of the DS (in L/h),
 210 Q_{Di1} is the inlet flow rate of the DS (in L/h), and C_P is the permeate concentration
 211 (in mg/L). Eventually, C_{Do1} was calculated from replacing the value of C_{Di1} from
 212 equation 11 in equation 8. The power density, W_1 (in W/m^2), was calculated from
 213 equation 12 as follows:

$$214$$

$$215 \quad W_1 = J_{w1} * \Delta P \quad [12]$$

216
 217 The power generation, P_w (in kW), by the PRO process was calculated from the
 218 following equation:

$$219$$

$$220 \quad P_w = Q_{P1} * \Delta P \quad [13]$$

221
 222 Finally, the PRO recovery rate, Re_1 , was calculated from the following equation:

$$223$$

$$224 \quad Re_1 = \frac{Q_{P1}}{Q_{F1}} \quad [14]$$

225
 226 where, Q_{F1} is the feed flow rate (in L/h).

227
 228 In the case of the dual stage, the diluted DS from the first stage of the DSPRO
 229 process is divided into two streams after leaving the membrane [see Figure 1B].
 230 The first stream goes back to a pressure exchanger to pressurize the DS. The
 231 second stream, with a volume equals to Q_{P1} , will be the draw solution of the
 232 second stage of the DSPRO process [Figure 2B]. This means that the flow rate of
 233 the DS in the second stage is equal to Q_{P1} . Furthermore, the hydraulic pressure
 234 of the first stage is equal to that of the second stage of the DSPRO process,
 235 assuming insignificant pressure losses in the first stage. The performance of the
 236 second stage of the PRO process was estimated using the following
 237 assumptions:

- 238
- 239 1. Membrane area in the second stage of the DSPRO process is calculated
 240 as the ratio of osmotic pressure driving force of the second stage to that of
 241 the first stage multiplied by A_{m1} ; i.e. $A_{m2} = A_{m1}(\Delta\pi_2 / \Delta\pi_1)$.
- 242 2. Osmotic pressure of the DS in the second stage is equal to the osmotic
 243 pressure of the diluted DS from the first stage since the diluted DS from
 244 the first stage is the DS of the second stage of the DSPRO process.
- 245 3. The osmotic pressure of FS is negligible (distilled water).

246
 247 The membrane flux in the second stage of the DSPRO process, J_{w2} , could be
 248 initially estimated from the solution diffusion model:

$$249$$

$$250 \quad J_{w2} = A_w(\Delta\pi - \Delta P) \quad [15]$$

251

252 where, A_w is the water permeability coefficient (in L/m²h.bar), $\Delta\pi$ is the osmotic
 253 pressure gradient (in bar), and ΔP is the hydraulic pressure difference (in bar).
 254 Likewise, the permeate flow rate in the second stage of the PRO process, Q_{P2} ,
 255 was calculated as:

$$256 \quad 257 \quad Q_{P2} = J_{w2} * A_{m2} \quad [16]$$

258 where A_{m2} is the membrane area in the second stage of the DSPRO process (in
 259 m²). Noting that, Q_{Do2} is the sum of Q_{Di2} and Q_{P2} . Assuming $C_{P2} \ll C_{Di2}$, the
 260 outlet concentration of the draw solution, C_{Do2} , was calculated from the
 261 concentration and mass balance on the DS side of the second stage of the
 262 DSPRO membrane:
 263

$$264 \quad 265 \quad C_{Do2} = \frac{Q_{Di2} * C_{Di2}}{Q_{Do2}} \quad [17]$$

266 where, C_{Di2} is the concentration of the DS in second stage (in mg/L). The outlet
 267 osmotic pressure of the DS, π_{Do2} (in bar), was calculated from the following
 268 equation:
 269

$$270 \quad 271 \quad \pi_{Do2} = \frac{C_{Do2} * \frac{Mw_{Na}}{Mw_{NaCl}} * 1.12 * T}{Mw_{Na} * 14.5} + \frac{C_{Do2} * \frac{Mw_{Cl}}{Mw_{NaCl}} * 1.12 * T}{Mw_{Cl} * 14.5} \quad [18]$$

272 where, Mw_{NaCl} is the molecular weight of NaCl (in mg/mol). The bulk
 273 concentration of the DS, π_{Db2} , was estimated from the following equation:
 274

$$275 \quad 276 \quad \pi_{Db2} = \frac{\pi_{Di2} + \pi_{Do2}}{2} \quad [19]$$

277 where π_{Di2} is the inlet osmotic pressure of the DS in the second stage (in bar).
 278 Then, the membrane flux of the second stage of the DSPRO, J_{w2} , was estimated
 279 from equation 20:
 280

$$281 \quad 282 \quad J_{w2} = A_w \left(\frac{\pi_{Db2} * e^{\frac{-J_{w2}}{k}} - \pi_{Fb2} * e^{J_{w2}K}}{1 + \frac{B}{J_{w2}} (e^{J_{w2}K} - e^{\frac{-J_{w2}}{k}})} - \Delta P \right) \quad [20]$$

283 In this case, the power density, W_2 (in W/m²), was estimated from equation 21:
 284

$$285 \quad 286 \quad W_2 = J_{w2} * \Delta P \quad [21]$$

287

288 The power generation of the second stage of the DSPRO, P_{w2} (in kWh), and the
 289 recovery rate, Re_2 (%), were estimated from equations 22 and 23, respectively:

291
$$P_{w2} = Q_{P2} * \Delta P \quad [22]$$

293
$$Re_2 = \frac{Q_{P2}}{Q_{F2}} \quad [23]$$

294 where, Q_{F2} is the feed flow rate of the second stage of the DSPRO process (L/h).
 295 The performance of the second stage of the PRO process was estimated by
 296 applying the iteration method described in [Figure 2].
 297
 298

299

300 Figure 2: Schematic diagram that illustrates the steps for estimating the
301 performance of the second stage of the PRO process
302

303 **2.2 Thermal system**

304
305 The main option that has been considered for regeneration of draw solution is
306 Multiple Effect Distillation (MED) which represents the most efficient evaporative
307 technology in the desalination industry [33-34]. The potential for improving its
308 energy efficiency is large, especially by increasing the operating temperature
309 over 70°C. Higher operating temperatures will result in the precipitation of
310 sparingly-soluble metal salts in the seawater. We assumed that a source of
311 waste heat is already available for the MED regeneration process.
312

313 The MED process consists in a series of under vacuum evaporators (also called
314 effects) at decreasing pressure and temperatures, in which vapour is generated
315 in one effect and condensed in the following one. The thermal energy source that
316 drives the evaporation process in all effects is the vapour generated in the
317 previous effect, except in the first one where an external heat source is required.
318 Distillate is obtained in all evaporators from the condensation of the vapour and
319 then it is directed to flash boxes in order to exploit its heat content. The remaining
320 feed water that has not been evaporated passes from one effect to other hence
321 gets more concentrated.
322

323 The MED system simulated in this work is forward-feed (see Figure 3). In this
324 design, the vapour and feed solution go in the same direction, from the highest
325 temperature effect to the lowest temperature effect. Another characteristic of this
326 design is the preheating of feed solution before the starting point of the process.
327 Shell and tube heat exchangers are used; feed solution circulates inside the
328 tubes and a small part of the vapour generated from the evaporator condenses
329 on the external surface to produce distillate and preheats the feed.
330

331 A computer model was developed to calculate the MED performance based on
332 energy and mass balances of the feed streams [35-36]. The model was validated
333 taking into account operating conditions such as Top Brine Temperature (TBT),
334 inlet salinity and recovery ratio [36]. For the current study, model operation
335 conditions were modified hence allowing for higher TBT and recovery ratios than
336 those for seawater desalination, since no fouling is expected in the process of DS
337 regeneration. The computation of model as well as the equations and the
338 considered boundary conditions are explained below.
339

Figure 3: Layout of the forward-feed MED plant considered in this work.

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356

There are two options for the design models of MED plants: firstly, to establish equal areas in all the effects and secondly, to consider constant temperature difference across the effects. The first option is used for constraining the size of the effects which is desired to decrease the capital cost of the MED. In this model, unlike that described in our previous work [36], equal area in all effects was considered. For the computation of the model, an iteration loop was implemented in the Matlab software that starts with the temperature profile and continues until a convergence criterion is achieved. The convergence criterion of the model should have a maximum difference in effect areas of $1 \cdot 10^{-4}$ in order to achieve a good accuracy.

The temperature profile was initially obtained considering equal temperature difference ($\Delta T_{eff,i}$) in all the effects, which was determined as the following:

$$\Delta T_{eff,i} = \frac{T_{v,1} - T_{v,N}}{N - 1} \quad [24]$$

357
358
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where N is the number of effects, $T_{v,1}$ is the vapor temperature generated in the 1st effect and $T_{v,N}$ is the vapor temperature generated in the last effect. The Top Brine Temperature (TBT) is the maximum temperature reached in the first evaporator, which corresponds to the maximum temperature of the un-evaporated brine solution through the MED ($T_{b,1}$). This temperature is higher than that of the vapour generated in the evaporator ($T_{v,1}$) due to the boiling point elevation (BPE). This parameter increases with the increase in the content of salts in the treated solution. For the rest of evaporators, the brine temperature

366 was also determined by the temperature of vapour produced inside the
367 evaporator and the corresponding BPE.

368

369 The performance of the MED plant is evaluated by the Recovery Ratio (RR) and
370 the specific thermal consumption, S_{TC} . On one hand, the recovery ratio is the
371 ratio of the distillate product to the feed flow rate supplied:

372

$$RR = \frac{M_{prod}}{M_f} \quad [25]$$

373

374 where M_{prod} is the total distillate flow rate obtained from the MED plant.

375

376 On the other hand, the specific thermal consumption is defined as the thermal
377 energy supplied to the distillation unit for every m^3 of distillate produced:

378

$$S_{TC} = \frac{Q_{eff,1}}{M_{prod}} \quad [26]$$

379

380 The total distillate flow rate was determined as the sum of the flows leaving the
381 flash boxes (see Appendix 1):

382

$$M_{prod} = \sum_{i=2}^N M_{d,i} \quad [27]$$

383

384 The heat transfer provided to the first effect ($Q_{eff,1}$) was calculated by the energy
385 balance equation as in the following equation:

386

$$Q_{eff,1} = M_{gb,1}\lambda_{gb,1} + M_f C_p (T_{b,1} - T_f) = M_s \lambda_s \quad [28]$$

387

388 where T_f is the temperature of feed water sprayed in the first effect of MED, M_s is
389 the mass flow rate of low pressure steam and λ_s is the change in enthalpy related
390 to the vapour condensation.

391

392 The model was run considering the salinity and feed solution flow rate to the
393 MED plant and the recovery ratio as inputs. The first two are given by the
394 characteristics of the DS as it exits the PRO, and the third is the required
395 concentration for the regeneration. The model results give first the number of
396 effects (N) and the TBT that keep the temperature difference between the MED
397 effects ($\Delta T_{eff,i}$) in the range of 2-3 °C, which is the usual driving force used in
398 MED plants to achieve good thermal efficiencies. Then, it gives the specific
399 thermal energy consumption, the area of the evaporators and the temperature
400 profile through the evaporators.

401

402 The following assumptions were considered in the model:

- 403
- 404 - Temperature difference of cooling water between the inlet ($T_{cw,in}$) and the
- 405 outlet ($T_{cw,out}$) through the end condenser was 7.3 °C
- 406 - Cooling water inlet temperature ($T_{cw,in}$) was 25 °C
- 407 - The temperature difference between the feed solution (T_f) and the vapour
- 408 generated inside 1st effect ($T_{v,1}$) was 3 °C.
- 409 - The initial (before the iteration loop) temperature difference between the
- 410 low pressure steam (T_s) and the vapour in the 1st effect ($T_{v,1}$) was
- 411 established as 4 °C. Then, it changed once and the new temperature
- 412 profile was generated by the equal effect areas iteration loop.
- 413

414 3. Results and discussion

415 3.1 Model Calibration

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417

418 The PRO model was calibrated using experimental data [12]. The membrane

419 flux, J_w , and the power density, W , were calculated and compared with the

420 experimental results [22], using draw solution pressures close to the optimum

421 value of $\Delta P = \Delta\pi / 2$. In order to evaluate the impact of the draw solution pressure

422 on the accuracy of the PRO model, a wide range of hydraulic pressures was

423 used for the calibration of the PRO model in the current study. Table 1 shows the

424 testing parameters for calibrating the PRO model using a cellulose triacetate FO

425 membrane manufactured by Hydration Technology Innovations, USA [22]. It was

426 assumed that the same type of PRO membrane was used in the first and the

427 second stage of the DSPRO process.

428

429

430 Table 1: PRO model testing parameters

Parameter	k (m/h)	K (h/m)	A_w (m/h.bar)	B (m/h)
Value	0.306	115-125	6.7×10^{-4}	4×10^{-4}

431

432 J_w and W are the key performance parameters of the PRO process; these

433 parameters were calculated and compared with the experimental results [22].

434 The results showed that the experimental and model membrane fluxes, J_{w-exp} ,

435 and J_{w-mod} respectively, were in a good agreement with each other [Table 2]. The

436 percentage difference between J_{w-exp} , and J_{w-mod} , %Diff J_w , was between 2.5%

437 and 9.8%. Apparently, using feed pressures less than $\Delta\pi / 2$ did not affect the

438 model accuracy. Table 2 also shows that the difference between experimental

439 and model power density, W_{exp} and W_{mod} respectively, were between 3.5% and

440 9.7%. Generally, the difference between model and experimental power densities

441 was less than 10%. It should be noted that the difference between the model and

442 experimental could be due to the fact that the osmotic pressures of the feed

443 solutions in the experimental work were calculated by OLI Systems Inc. (Morris

444 Plains, NJ) while the osmotic pressures of the feed solutions in the model were
 445 determined by Van't Hoff equation.

446

447

448 Table 2: Model and experimental data of membrane flux and power density

449 * draw solution pressure $\Delta\pi/2$

Draw TDS (g/L)	Feed TDS (g/L)	Pressure (bar)	$J_{w\text{-exp}}$ (L/m ² h)	$J_{w\text{-mod}}$ (L/m ² h)	% Diff. J_w	W_{exp} (W/m ²)	W_{mod} (W/m ²)	% Diff. W
35*	0	13	7.9	7.7	2.5%	2.9	2.8	3.5%
	2.5	12	6.8	6.2	8.8%	2.3	2.1	8.7%
	5	11	5.6	5.1	8.9%	1.7	1.55	8.8%
60*	0	24	12.4	12	3.5%	8.3	8.0	3.6%
	2.5	23	10.1	9.5	5.9%	6.5	6.1	6.1%
	5	22.5	8.5	7.8	8.2%	5.3	4.9	7.5%
35	0	10	10.1	9.4	6.9%	2.8	2.6	7.1%
	2.5	10	7.2	6.7	7.0%	2.0	1.85	7.5%
	5	10	5.5	5.1	7.2%	1.6	1.4	6.7%
60	0	15	15.8	15	5.0%	6.8	6.3	7.3%
	2.5	15	12.2	11	9.8%	5.0	4.6	8.8%
	5	15	9.6	8.9	7.2%	4.1	3.7	9.7%

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453 3.2 Single and dual PRO system

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455 The PRO process optimization was performed taking into account the impact of
 456 the membrane area, draw solution pressure, and DS flow rate. The performance
 457 of single and dual stage CLPRO was evaluated for comparison purposes. The
 458 effect of changing the membrane area on the performance of a single and dual
 459 stage CLPRO process is illustrated in [Figure 4]. The applied draw solution
 460 pressure was 16 bar and the draw and feed solutions flow rates in the first stage
 461 of the PRO process were 5000 L/h. PRO mode membrane orientation was
 462 selected because of the higher PRO performance [21, 27]. For the single stage
 463 CLPRO, the increase of the membrane area resulted in a minor increase in the
 464 water flux of the first stage, J_{w1} . This was accomplished by increasing the inlet
 465 concentration of DS, C_{Di1} , and the osmotic pressure, π_{Di1} of the first stage [Figure
 466 4a and 4b]. J_{w1} increased from 11.2 L/m²h to 11.6 L/m²h as membrane area
 467 increased from 200 m² to 300 m², respectively, because of the larger permeate
 468 flow. The corresponding inlet DS concentrations, C_{Di1} , were 0.86 mol/L and 0.92

469 mol/L, respectively. Practically, the modulus of external CP (ECP), $e^{\frac{-J_w}{k}}$, on the
 470 DS side of the membrane approaches a unity at negligible ECP. The results

471 show [Figure 4c] that $e^{\frac{-J_w}{k}}$ decreased slightly below a unity with the increase in
472 the membrane area indicating a higher ECP effect. Therefore, C_{Di1} was slightly
473 increased with the increase of membrane area in order to maintain J_{w1} [Figure 4a
474 and 4b].

475
476 For a DSPRO process, the high membrane flux in the first stage increased the
477 dilution of DS which in turn affected the water flux in the second stage of the
478 DSPRO, J_{w2} [Figure 4a]. Simulation results show that J_{w2} decreased from 5.0
479 L/m²h to 4.0 L/m²h due to the increase of first stage membrane area, A_{m1} , from
480 200 m² to 300 m². This was attributed to the lower osmotic pressure across the
481 PRO membrane. The osmotic pressure of the DS in the second stage, π_{Di2} ,
482 decreased from 26 bar to 23.7 bar whereas C_{Di2} decreased from 0.58 mol/L to
483 0.52 mol/L as A_{m1} increased from 200 m² to 300 m², respectively [Figure 4a and

484 4b]. Furthermore, simulation results revealed that $e^{\frac{-J_w}{k}}$ of the second stage of the
485 DSPRO process increased from 0.98 to 0.99 with the increase in the membrane
486 area, which was an indicative to the lower CP effect. In effect, the decrease of
487 J_{w2} resulted in a lower dilutive ECP at the DS side of the second stage of the
488 CLPRO process.

489
490 Recovery rates of the first and second stage of the CLPRO process are
491 illustrated in [Figure 4d]. Results reveal that the recovery rates of the first and the
492 second stage of the DSPRO, Re_1 and Re_2 , increased with the increase in the
493 A_{m1} . In this way, Re_1 was 45% at 200 m² membrane area and increased to 70%
494 at 300 m², whereas Re_2 increased from 27% to 51% as A_{m1} increased from 200
495 m² to 300 m². The total recovery rate of the DSPRO, Re_{-tot} , was 60% at 200 m²
496 and increased to 85% at 300 m². Furthermore, the power density of the first and
497 second stage, W_1 and W_2 respectively, were estimated and illustrated in [Figure
498 4e]. Simulation results revealed that W_1 increased from 6 W/m² to 6.5 W/m² as
499 A_{m1} increased from 200 m² to 300 m², whereas W_2 decreased from 2.8 W/m² to
500 2.3 W/m² as A_{m1} increased from 200 m² to 300 m² [Figure 4e]. The increase and
501 decrease, respectively, of W_1 and W_2 , reflected the increase and decrease of J_{w1}
502 and J_{w2} , respectively. The higher the water flux the higher the power density
503 produced by the PRO membrane. Finally, results show that W_2 was 45% of W_1
504 at 200 m² and decreased to 35% of W_1 at 300 m². For the rest of this study, A_{m1}
505 was assumed 300 m² because of the high PRO performance and power density,
506 especially in the first stage; i.e. ($W_1 \sim 3W_2$).

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Figure 4: Impact of membrane area on single and dual stage PRO process a) impact on the water flux and DS concentration b) effect of inlet and outlet concentration of DS of single and dual stage CLPRO c) effect on dilutive concentration polarization d) effect on recovery rate of single and dual stage CLPRO e) effect on power density

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The effect of hydraulic pressure, P , on the performance of the first and second stages of the DSPRO process is illustrated in [Figure 5]. The performance of the CLPRO process was modelled for a membrane area of 300 m² and 5000L/h for Q_{Di1} and Q_{Fi1} . Water flux of the first stage of the DSPRO process, J_{W1} , increased from 7.2 L/m²h to 11.6 L/m²h as draw solution pressure increased from 10 bar to 16 bar, respectively [Figure 5a]. This was due to the increase of the inlet concentration of DS, C_{Di1} , and the osmotic pressure, π_{Di1} , of the first stage of the DSPRO process. For example, C_{Di1} increased from 0.5 mol/L to 0.9 mol/L as the draw solution pressure increased from 10 bar to 16 bar; the corresponding π_{Di1}

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was 24 bar and 40 bar, respectively [Figure 5b]. For a PRO process operating at maximum power density, the draw solution pressure increased with the increase in the osmotic pressure of the salinity gradient resource. In effect, the increase of C_{Di1} was essential to provide a sufficient driving force for the increase of J_{W1} . Furthermore, the effect of the draw solution pressure on the ECP of the first stage was illustrated in [Figure 5c]. $e^{-\frac{J_w}{k}}$ function deviated away from a unity with the increase in the draw solution pressure, which indicated a high ECP effect.

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For the second stage of the DSPRO process, increasing the draw solution pressure from 10 bar to 16 bar resulted in a slight increase of J_{W2} from 3.2 L/m²h

548 to 4.1 L/m²h. This was attributed to the increase of C_{Di2} and π_{Di2} , which resulted
 549 in a higher J_{w2} [Figures 5a and 5b]. Furthermore, $e^{\frac{-J_w}{k}}$ was decreased slightly
 550 below a unity as an indicative of the higher ECP effect on the DS side, which was
 551 caused by the high J_{w2} [Figure 5c]. The results also show that the recovery rate of
 552 first and second stage, Re_1 and Re_2 respectively, increased with the increase of
 553 the draw solution pressure from 10 bar to 16 bar. The total recovery rate of the
 554 DSPRO, i.e. the sum of Re_1 and Re_2 , increased from 58% to 85% due to the
 555 increase of draw solution pressure from 10 bar to 16 bar. Regarding PRO power
 556 density, the results are shown in [Figure 5e]. W_1 increased about 2.5 times, from
 557 2.5 W/m² to 6.46 W/m², due to the draw solution pressure increase from 10 bar
 558 to 16 bar whereas W_2 was doubled, from 1.1 W/m² to 2.3 W/m², due to the
 559 increase of draw solution pressure from 10 bar to 16 bar. In general, W_2 was
 560 about 45% and 35% of W_1 at draw solution pressures 10 bar and 16 bar,
 561 respectively. The results show that the performance of the DSPRO process was
 562 higher at a draw solution pressure of 16 bar and a A_{m1} of 300 m².
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Figure 5: Impact of draw solution pressure on the single and DSPRO performance a) effect on the water flux and draw solution concentration b) effect of inlet and outlet concentration of DS of single and dual stage CLPRO c) effect on dilutive concentration polarization d) effect on the recovery rate of single and dual stage CLPRO e) effect on power density

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The effect of the DS flow rate on the performance of CLPRO process was evaluated at a draw solution pressure of 16 bar and a membrane area of 300 m² [Figure 6]. The simulation results revealed that the J_{w1} remained constant, about 11.6 L/m²h, despite the increase in the DS flow rate from 2000 L/h to 5000 L/h [Figure 6a]. Previous studies demonstrated that the water flux increases with the increase of the DS flow rate, Q_{Di1} , due to the higher bulk osmotic pressure of the DS [30, 37]. At the present study, C_{Di1} and π_{Di1} decreased with the increase in the Q_{Di1} ; C_{Di1} and π_{Di1} were decreased to maintain a constant J_{w1} across the PRO membrane [Figure 6a and 6b]. As such, the concentration of draw solution can be decreased at high flow rates; this operating condition would reduce the effect of CP but on the expense of slightly higher pumping energy.

For the second stage, the increase of Q_{Di1} resulted in an increase of J_{w2} [Figure 6a]. This was attributed to the increase of the concentration and osmotic pressure of the DS in the second stage of DSPRO [Figure 6b]. J_{w2} was 1.6 L/m²h and 4.2 L/m²h at 2500 L/h and 5000 L/h Q_{Di1} respectively; the corresponding C_{Di2} for 2500 L/h and 5000 L/h Q_{Di1} was 0.42 mol/L and 0.52 mol/L, respectively

[Figure 6b]. $e^{-\frac{J_w}{k}}$ of the first stage of the DSPRO remained unaffected by Q_{Di1} change indicating a constant ECP, whereas J_{w2} increased with the increase of

Q_{Di1} and it resulted in a higher $e^{-\frac{J_w}{k}}$ effect at 5000 L/h Q_{Di1} [Figure 6c]. For the second stage of the DSPRO process, the outlet concentration of DS, C_{Do2} , increased from 0.39 mol/L to 0.42 mol/L due to the increase of Q_{Di1} from 2500 L/h to 5000 L/h [Figure 6b].

For the first stage, Re_1 remained constant at 70% with the increase in Q_{Di1} [Figure 6d]. However, the recovery rate of the second stage, Re_2 , increased from 14% to 51% as a result of the increase in Q_{Di1} from 2500 L/h to 5000 L/h [Figure 6d]. This was attributed to the higher permeation flow in the second stage of the DSPRO. Re_{tot} of the DSPRO process also increased with the increase of Q_{Di1} and it reached 85% at a Q_{Di1} of 4500 L/h. Finally, the power density of the first and second stage of the DSPRO process is illustrated in [Figure 6e]. W_1 was unaffected by the variation of Q_{Di1} from 2500 L/m² to 5000 L/m². On the contrary, W_2 increased from 0.9 W/m² to 2.3 W/m² due to the increase in Q_{Di1} from 2500 L/m² to 5000 L/m². W_2 was about 20% to 70% of W_1 at 2500 L/m² and 5000 L/m² Q_{Di1} respectively. As such, W_2 was almost negligible at a Q_{Di1} of 2000 L/m². This suggests that reducing Q_{Di1} can significantly affect the performance of the second stage of the CLPRO process and hence it should be avoided. As such, a Q_{Di1} of 5000 L/m² was selected due to the higher performance of the DSPRO process.

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 637 Figure 6: Impact of draw solution flow rate on the performance of single and dual
 638 stage PRO process a) effect on the water flux and DS concentration b) effect of
 639 inlet and outlet concentration of DS of single and dual stage CLPRO c) effect on
 640 dilutive concentration polarization d) recovery rate effect on single and dual stage
 641 CLPRO e) effect on power density
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643 The results showed that dual stage CLPRO performed better than the single
 644 stage CLPRO at all operating conditions. But it should be observed that the draw
 645 solution pressure and the DS flow rate were the most influential parameters in
 646 the first and second stage of the DSPRO, respectively, whereas the membrane
 647 area had low impact on the process performance. In practical terms, the pressure
 648 of the draw solution would be fixed at $\Delta\pi/2$ in order to increase the power
 649 generation of the first stage while the flow rate of the DS should be increased to
 650 enhance the performance of the second stage of the DSPRO process.
 651 Furthermore, the concentration of draw solution can be decreased at high draw
 652 solution flow rates. The percentage of W_1 and W_2 variation with the membrane
 653 area, draw solution pressure and DS flow rate are presented in Table 3. The
 654 values shown in column 6 and 7 were calculated as the percentage difference
 655 with the upper value of each stage. In general, the draw solution pressure is the
 656 most influential parameter in the first stage followed by draw solution flow rate
 657 and membrane area, respectively. For example, 61% increase in W_1 was
 658 achieved due to the increase of draw solution pressure from 10 bar to 16 bar.
 659 However, the concentration of draw solution should be increased at high draw
 660 solution pressures to maintain enough osmotic potential across the membrane.
 661 For the second stage of the DSPRO, DS flow rate was the most influential
 662 parameter followed by the draw solution pressure and membrane area,

663 respectively. About the 61% increase of W_2 occurred due to the increase of the
 664 DS flow rate from 2500 L/h to 5000 L/h.

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666 Also, the simulation results showed that W_1 was 2 to 3 times more than W_2
 667 indicating that the DSPRO efficiency is mainly based on the performance of the
 668 first stage of the DSPRO. These model results show the influence of membrane
 669 area, draw solution pressure and draw solution flow rate on the power density of
 670 the CLPRO process, thus they can be used in the design of the single and dual
 671 stage CLPRO plant and the system optimization to reduce the capital and
 672 operating costs.

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674 Table 3: Impact of operating parameters on the inlet concentration of draw
 675 solution to the single and dual stage CLPRO process and power density of single
 676 and dual stage CLPRO process

Parameter	C_{Di1} (mol/L)	C_{Di2} (mol/L)	W_1 (W/m ²)	W_2 (W/m ²)	% Diff W_1 stage 1	% Diff W_2 stage 2
A (m ²)						
200	0.84	0.58	6.20	2.84	-3.9%	0.0%
220	0.85	0.57	6.27	2.74	-2.9%	3.7%
240	0.86	0.56	6.33	2.63	-2.0%	7.5%
260	0.87	0.54	6.38	2.52	-1.2%	11.3%
280	0.88	0.53	6.42	2.42	-0.6%	15.1%
300	0.89	0.52	6.46	2.31	0.0%	18.9%
P (bar)						
10	0.52	0.36	2.52	1.13	-61.0%	-50.8%
11	0.58	0.39	3.05	1.33	-52.7%	-42.6%
12	0.64	0.42	3.63	1.52	-43.8%	-34.1%
13	0.70	0.45	4.26	1.72	-34.0%	-25.6%
14	0.76	0.47	4.94	1.92	-23.4%	-17.0%
15	0.83	0.50	5.67	2.11	-12.1%	-8.4%
16	0.89	0.52	6.46	2.31	0.0%	0.0%
Q_{Di1} (L/h)						
2500	1.00	0.42	6.46	0.90	-	-60.9%
3000	0.97	0.45	6.46	1.34	-	-42.0%
3500	0.94	0.47	6.46	1.67	-	-27.6%
4000	0.92	0.49	6.46	1.93	-	-16.4%
4500	0.90	0.51	6.46	2.14	-	-7.4%
5000	0.89	0.52	6.46	2.31	-	0.0%

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680 3.3 MED regeneration system

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682 The MED model described in Section 2.3 was considered for the draw solution
 683 regeneration. The effect of PRO membrane area on the MED performance was
 684 evaluated using 16 bar as the draw solution pressure and a draw solution flow
 685 rate of 5000 L/h [Figure 7]. The recovery rate of the MED process increased with
 686 the increase of the PRO membrane area [Figure 7a]. At a membrane area of 300

687 m^2 , the maximum recovery rate of single stage CLPRO, Re_1 , was 46.5% which is
688 8% lower than the recovery rate of the dual stage CLPRO, Re_2 . The TBT of the
689 MED plant was 73 °C at Re_1 of 46.5%, and increased to 76 °C at Re_2 of 50.2%
690 [Figure 7a]. For a single stage PRO process, TBT increased from 67 °C to 73 °C
691 due to the increase of Re_1 from 35.8% to 46.5%, respectively. For a dual stage
692 CLPRO process, TBT was 71 °C and 76 °C at Re_2 40.7% and 50.2%,
693 respectively. Therefore, the TBT for a single stage CLPRO was 4% and 6% lower
694 than that for a dual stage CLPRO process at a draw solution pressure of 10 bar
695 and 16 bar, respectively. Dual stage CLPRO process, in practice, requires higher
696 TBT than single stage PRO due to the higher recovery rates achieved by the
697 former process. The Specific Thermal Consumption (S_{TC}) represents the thermal
698 power required for saline water purification. Figure 8b shows the S_{TC} for the
699 regeneration of DS in a single and dual stage CLPRO. S_{TC} for a single stage was
700 higher than that for a dual stage CLPRO process [Figure 7b]. S_{TC} for the single
701 stage CLPRO process decreased from 67 kWh/m³ at 200 m² to 51 kWh/m³ at
702 300 m². For the dual stage CLPRO process, S_{TC} decreased from 61 kWh/m³ at
703 200 m² to 48 kWh/m³ at 300 m². The results reveal that S_{TC} for the dual stage
704 CLPRO was lower than that for the single stage. However, that was on the
705 expense of the higher heat transfer area, A_{eff} , required for the dual stage CLPRO
706 process [Figure 7b], which is disadvantageous due to the fact that the increase of
707 the A_{eff} lead to a rise in the capital cost of the MED process. Results in Table 4
708 show the number of effects of MED plant suggested for draw solution
709 regeneration. Obviously, the number of effects of the MED plant for the
710 regeneration of DS from a dual stage CLPRO was higher than that for the single
711 stage CLPRO process. This also suggests that the MED capital cost for draw
712 solution regeneration would be higher in the case of a dual stage CLPRO
713 process. $P_{W\text{-MED}}$ represents the electric energy required for the draw solution
714 regeneration by the MED process, which is considered about 1.2 kWh/m³ [39].
715 The ratio of $P_{W\text{-PRO}}/P_{W\text{-MED}}$ was 103% and 127% for the single and dual stage
716 CLPRO, respectively [Figure 7c]. $P_{W\text{-PRO}}/P_{W\text{-MED}}$ ratio over hundred was an
717 indicative of a positive power generation; i.e. power generation by CLPRO is
718 higher than the power consumption for the regeneration of DS. Results show that
719 the $P_{W\text{-PRO}}/P_{W\text{-MED}}$ ratio increased to 162% and 186% for the single and dual
720 stage CLPRO, respectively. Apparently, the energy efficiency of the dual stage
721 CLPRO was higher than that of the single stage, which will potentially pay off for
722 the higher capital cost of the dual stage CLPRO system.
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Figure 7: Impact of CLPRO membrane area on the specifications of MED thermal plant a) effect on recovery rate and TBT b) effect on specific thermal consumption and heat transfer area c) effect of membrane area on the energy efficiency

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The impact of the draw solution pressure on the performance of the MED regeneration plant was evaluated using a membrane area of 300 m² and a Q_{Di1} of 5000 L/h [Figure 8]. Re_1 and Re_2 increased with the increase in the PRO membrane area. However, Re_2 was 16% higher than Re_1 at a draw solution pressure of 10 bar. The TBT required for the DS regeneration in a dual stage CLPRO was higher than that required in a single stage CLPRO [Figure 8a]. Furthermore, at a draw solution pressure of 16 bar, Re_2 was 10% higher than Re_1 whereas the TBT required for the DS regeneration in the dual stage CLPRO was only 4% higher than that required for the DS regeneration in the single stage CLPRO. The TBT required for the regeneration of DS was 69 °C and 72 °C for the single and the dual stage CLPRO processes, respectively [Figure 8a]. These TBT's were almost within the range of operating temperatures required in the thermal energy source for commercial MED plants.

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The S_{TC} for the draw solution regeneration of the single stage CLPRO process was 77 kWh/m³ and 55 kWh/m³ at a draw solution pressure of 10 bar and 16 bar, respectively [Figure 8b]. This was higher than the S_{TC} required for the draw solution regeneration of the dual stage CLPRO process: 69 kWh/m³ and 51 kWh/m³ at 10 bar and 16 bar, respectively. Furthermore, the dual stage required slightly more A_{eff} than the single stage CLPRO process. It should be noticed that

756 the difference of A_{eff} between the single stage and the dual stage CLPRO
 757 process decreased at a draw solution pressure of 16 bar [Figure 8c]. Table 4
 758 shows the number of effects of the MED plant, in which it can be seen that
 759 between 11 and 15 effects were required for the regeneration of DS in the single
 760 stage CLPRO whereas between 12 and 18 effects were required in the MED for
 761 the regeneration of DS in the dual stage CLPRO.

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763 The results also showed a P_{W-PRO}/P_{W-MED} ratio over a hundred percent,
 764 indicating a positive power generation, i.e. power generation by the CLPRO was
 765 higher than the electric power consumption by the MED process for regenerating
 766 the DS [Figure 8c]. For the single and dual stage CLPRO, the P_{W-PRO}/P_{W-MED}
 767 ratio increased with the increase of the draw solution pressure from 10 bar to 16
 768 bar. At a draw solution pressure of 16 bar, the ratio of P_{W-PRO}/P_{W-MED} was 132%
 769 and 157% for the single and dual stage CLPRO process, respectively. Indeed,
 770 the dual stage CLPRO process was more energy efficient than the single stage
 771 process. It should be noted that the difference of the P_{W-PRO}/P_{W-MED} ratio between
 772 the single and dual stage CLPRO process increased with the increase in the feed
 773 pressure. Thus, the efficiency of the dual stage CLPRO process increases with
 774 the increase in the feed pressure.

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Figure 8: Impact of CLPRO draw solution pressure on the specifications of MED thermal plant a) effect on recovery rate and TBT b) effect on specific thermal consumption and heat transfer area c) effect of membrane area on the energy efficiency

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788 Figure 9 shows the impact of the draw solution flow rate, Q_{Di1} , on the
789 performance of the CLPRO process at a draw solution pressure of 16 bar and a
790 PRO membrane area of 300 m². Re_1 and Re_2 decreased with the increase in Q_{Di1}
791 from 2500 L/h to 5000 L/h. However, Re_2 was always higher than Re_1 but the
792 difference between Re_1 and Re_2 increased with the increase in Q_{Di1} [Figure 9a].
793 Furthermore, the TBT of the MED regeneration process for the single stage
794 CLPRO process was unaffected by the increase of Q_{Di1} . However, this was on
795 the expense of higher S_{TC} at high Q_{Di1} [Table 4]. In the case of the dual stage
796 CLPRO process, the TBT of the MED was very sensitive to the change of Q_{Di1} . In
797 general, the TBT of the MED unit treating a diluted draw solution from a single
798 stage CLPRO process was lower than that from a dual stage CLPRO process. At
799 a draw solution pressure of 16 bar, the TBT of the MED plant was 72 °C and 76
800 °C for a single and dual stage CLPRO, respectively. These TBTs were slightly
801 higher than that normally used in the commercial MED plants. The results also
802 revealed that the S_{TC} for the DS regeneration from the single stage CLPRO
803 process was higher than that for the DS regeneration from the dual stage CLPRO
804 [Figure 9b]. However, A_{eff} of the MED was higher for the dual stage CLPRO
805 [Figure 9b] but the difference in A_{eff} between the single stage and the dual stage
806 CLPRO process slightly decreased with the increase in the Q_{Di1} . Thus, applying
807 high draw solution flow rates would decrease the capital cost of the MED plant.

808

809 The ratio of P_{W-PRO}/P_{W-MED} for a single stage CLPRO process remained constant
810 at 161% despite the increase of Q_{Di1} [Figure 9c]. For the dual stage CLPRO, the
811 ratio of P_{W-PRO}/P_{W-MED} was 171% at 2500 L/h but increased to 195% at 5000 L/h
812 Q_{Di1} . This suggests that dual stage CLPRO process was more energy efficient
813 than the single stage CLPRO process especially at higher Q_{Di1} . At 5000 L/h Q_{Di1} ,
814 the ratio of P_{W-PRO}/P_{W-MED} for the dual stage CLPRO was 21% higher than that for
815 the single stage CLPRO process. MED regeneration of the DS resulted in a
816 positive PRO power generation assuming that the power consumption in the
817 MED process was mainly electrical whereas thermal energy provided by a source
818 of waste heat.

819

820 The dual stage CLPRO process is more energy efficient than the single stage
821 CLPRO but it requires higher TBT and heat transfer area for the regeneration of
822 the draw solution by the MED process. The range of TBT for the regeneration of
823 DS was between 67 °C and 75 °C for the dual stage CLPRO which will not affect
824 the operation cost of the MED plant if a free source of waste heat is available.
825 Interestingly, the S_{TC} of MED for treatment of DS from the dual stage CLPRO
826 was lower than that of MED for treatment of DS from the single stage CLPRO.
827 This emphasizes the superiority of dual stage CLPRO process over the single
828 stage CLPRO process. The results suggest that dual stage CLPRO coupling with
829 the MED process can be a viable option for power generation from a salinity
830 gradient resource. The system can be also used for energy storage. In this case,
831 a source of thermal energy would be applied for the regeneration of draw and

832 feed solution by the MED process. This energy can be recovered later on by
833 pairing the draw and feed solutions in the PRO process for power generation.
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Figure 9: Effect of CLPRO DS flow rate on the specifications of MED thermal plant a) effect on recovery rate and TBT b) effect on specific thermal consumption and heat transfer area c) effect of membrane area on the energy efficiency of single and dual stage CLPRO

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Table 4: Impact of CLPRO operating parameters on the specific thermal consumption and number of effects of the single and dual stage CLPRO process

Parameter	Single stage CLPRO		Dual stage CLPRO	
	S_{TC} kWh/m ³	No. Effects	S_{TC} kWh/m ³	No. Effects
A (m ²)				
200	66.99	13	61.2	14
220	62.73	14	57.72	15
240	59.17	15	54.74	16
260	56	16	52.08	17
280	53.29	17	49.81	18
300	50.85	18	47.76	19
P bar				
10	76.7	11	69.29	12
11	71.41	12	64.99	13
12	67.14	13	61.31	14
13	63.37	14	58.16	15
14	60.11	15	55.4	16
15	57.22	16	52.98	17
16	54.74	15	50.87	18
Q_{D1} L/h				
3000	58.16	14	55.08	15
3500	58.99	14	55.42	15
4000	59.59	14	55.79	15
4500	60.28	14	56.14	15
5000	60.83	14	56.47	15

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4. Conclusions

855 CLPRO process was suggested for power generation using single and dual stage
856 configuration. A computer model was developed to predict the performance of
857 the DSPRO process. The effect of membrane area, DS flow rate and draw
858 solution pressure on the performance of the DSPRO process was investigated.
859 Simulation results revealed that the effect of the draw solution pressure on the
860 performance of the first stage was higher than the effect of other parameters. On
861 the other hand, the DS flow rate was the most influential parameters in the
862 second stage. As such, the draw solution pressure needs to be optimized during
863 the design of a DSPRO process.

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Regardless the regeneration process, the dual stage CLPRO process
outperformed the single stage CLPRO process, which underlined the superiority
of the former system for power generation by osmotic energy. The power density
of the DSPRO process was 43% more than that generated by the single stage
CLPRO process. Furthermore, the simulation results showed that the MED

870 system requires about 3 °C higher temperature for the regeneration of the draw
 871 solution in the dual stage CLPRO process. This thermal process would be
 872 feasible as a heat engine when an affordable source of low grade heat is
 873 available. In terms of capital costs, it would be slightly higher in the case of dual
 874 stage CLPRO due to the larger membrane and heat transfer areas of the PRO-
 875 MED system but capital cost increase will be paid off over time due to the higher
 876 energy efficiency of the dual stage CLPRO process.

877

878 **Appendix 1: Equations of the MED model.**

879

880 The MED model is described elsewhere [36-37], but some equations have been
 881 particularized for this study.

882

883 The area of each evaporator ($A_{eff,i}$) was determined by calculating the
 884 temperature difference between the un-evaporated brine in the effect i ($T_{b,i}$) and
 885 the vapour that comes from the preceding effect and enters in the effect i ($T_{v,i-1}$),
 886 and the heat transfer rate provided to the effect i ($Q_{eff,i}$). Likewise, rate of heat
 887 transfer is equal to the change in enthalpy related to the condensation of the
 888 vapour coming from the previous effect and entering in the effect i ($\lambda_{v,i-1}$):

889

$$Q_{eff,i} = U_{eff,i} A_{eff,i} (T_{v,i-1} - T_{b,i}) = M_{v,i} \lambda_{v,i-1} \quad [A1]$$

890

891 where $U_{eff,i}$ is the total heat transfer coefficient, which is obtained by the
 892 correlation suggested in our previous work [37], and $M_{v,i}$ is the vapour mass flow
 893 rate going to the bundle tube of each effect, which consists of the total vapour
 894 generated by boiling of the brine ($M_{gb,i-1}$), flashing of the brine ($M_{gf,i-1}$) and
 895 flashing of the distilled water in the flash box ($M_{df,i-1}$), all of it minus the vapour
 896 consumed in the preheater ($M_{vh,i-1}$), as shown in the following equation:

897

$$M_{v,i} = (M_{gb,i-1} + M_{gf,i-1} + M_{df,i-1}) - M_{vh,i-1} \quad [A2]$$

898

899 Each mass flow rate of the previous equation (M), is determined by energy
 900 balances in the effects, the preheaters and the flash boxes.

901

902 The vapour consumed in the preheater, $M_{vh,i}$, is condensed releasing latent heat
 903 $\lambda_{vh,i}$ (at a temperature $T_{v,i}$) which is utilized to heat the feed water flowing through
 904 the preheaters tube bundle:

905

$$M_{vh,i} \lambda_{vh,i} = M_f C_p (T_{ph,i} - T_{ph,i+1}) \quad [A3]$$

906

907 where $T_{ph,i}$ is the feed water temperature in the bundle tube of a preheater i , and
 908 M_f is defined as the mass flow rate of feed solution sprayed in 1st effect.

909

910 In the case of preheaters, it was assumed an equal temperature difference
 911 between preheaters ($\Delta T_{preh,i}$), which is determined from the following expression:
 912

$$\Delta T_{preh,i} = \frac{T_{ph,1} - T_{ph,Nph}}{N_{ph}} \quad [A4]$$

913
 914 where N_{ph} is the number of preheaters, which is considered equal to $N - 1$.
 915

916 Additionally, mass flow rate of the vapour generated in each evaporator is
 917 obtained by the following energy balance:
 918

$$M_{gb,i} \lambda_{gb,i} = M_{v,i} \lambda_{v,i-1} + M_{db,i} C_p (T_{db,i} - T_{b,i}) \quad [A5]$$

919
 920 $M_{db,i}$ is the mass flow rate of the brine solution after flashing once it enters the
 921 effect (at a higher pressure than that one inside the effect), $\lambda_{gb,i}$ is the latent heat
 922 of vaporization at $T_{v,i}$ and $T_{db,i}$ is the un-evaporated brine temperature after
 923 flashing. $M_{db,i}$ was determined by the following mass balance:
 924

$$M_{db,i} = M_{b,i-1} - M_{gf,i} \quad [A6]$$

925
 926 The mass flow rate of the flashing brine was determined by an energy balance:
 927

$$M_{gf,i} \lambda_{gf,i} = M_{b,i-1} C_p (T_{b,i-1} - T_{db,i}) \quad [A7]$$

928
 929 where $\lambda_{gf,i}$ is the vaporization latent heat at $T_{v,i}$.
 930

931 Both mass flow rates (M_{gf} , M_{db}) were considered zero in the first effect, since in
 932 this case the feed solution enters at a temperature below saturation (sub-cooled);
 933 i.e. no vapour is produced by the flashing process.
 934

935 $M_{b,i}$ is the mass flow rate of the brine that leaves each effect and enters the
 936 following one and it was determined from the following equation:
 937

$$M_{b,i} = M_{db,i} - M_{gb,i} \quad [A8]$$

938
 939 Finally, the mass flow rate of the vapour produced through flashing of the
 940 distillate in each flash box was calculated by:
 941

$$M_{df,i} \lambda_{df,i} = M_{vh,i-1} C_p (T_{v,i-1} - T_{v,i}) + M_{v,i-1} C_p (T_{v,i-1} - T_{v,i}) + M_{d,i-1} C_p (T_{v,i-1} - T_{v,i}) \quad [A9]$$

942
 943 where $\lambda_{df,i}$ is the vaporization latent heat at $T_{v,i}$ and $M_{d,i}$ is the distillate mass flow
 944 rate leaving each flash box, which was determined from the following mass
 945 balance formula:

946

$$M_{d,i} = M_{v,i} + M_{vh,i-1} + M_{d,i-1} - M_{df,i} \quad [A10]$$

947

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950

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954

955

Abbreviations:

956

Abbreviation	Full Meaning
CLPRO	Closed-Loop Pressure Retarded Osmosis
MED	Multi-Effect Distillation
RO	Reverse Osmosis
PRO	Pressure Retarded Osmosis
RED	Reverse Electrodialysis
DS	Draw Solution
FS	Feed Solution
CP	Concentration Polarization
DSPRO	Dual Stage Pressure Retarded Osmosis
SSPRO	Standard Single Stage Pressure Retarded Osmosis
ERD	Energy Recovery Device
TBT	Top Brine Temperature
BPE	boiling point elevation
RR	Recovery Ratio
S _{TC}	Specific Thermal Consumption

957

958

Nomenclature

959

Nomenclature	Full Meaning
Q_p	PRO permeate flow rate (m ³ /h)
π_{Db}	osmotic pressure of the bulk draw solution (bar)
π_{Fb}	osmotic pressure of the feed draw solution (bar)
k	mass transfer coefficient (m/s)
A_m	PRO membrane area (m ²)
A_w	water permeability coefficient (L/m ² h bar)
ΔP	hydraulic pressure difference (bar)
$\Delta \pi$	osmotic pressure gradient (bar)
B	solute permeability coefficient (m/h)
K	solute resistivity for diffusion within porous support layer (s/m)
J_w	membrane flux (L/m ² h)
T	feed temperature (K)
m_n	molar concentration of n th ion species

$C_{Na,b}$	bulk concentration of Na ion (mg/L)
$C_{Cl,b}$	bulk concentration of Cl ion (mg/L)
MW_{Na}	molecular weight of Na (mg/M)
MW_{Cl}	molecular weight of Cl (mg/M)
C_{Di}	inlet concentration of draw solution (mg/L)
C_{Do}	outlet concentration of draw solution (mg/L)
Q_{Di}	inlet flow rate of draw solution (L/h)
Q_{Do}	outlet flow rate of draw solution (L/h)
C_p	permeate concentration (mg/L)
W	power density (W/m^2)
C_p	permeate concentration (mg/L)
P_w	power generation (kW)
Re	PRO recovery rate
Q_F	feed flow rate (L/h)
Q_P	permeate flow rate (L/h)
$\Delta\pi$	osmotic pressure gradient (bar)
$ES-RO$	specific power consumption of RO (kWh/m^3)
P_f	RO feed pressure (bar)
P_p	RO permeate pressure (bar)
P_{W-RO}	RO power consumption (kWh)
η	Pump efficiency
Q_{hpp}	feed flow rate of high pressure pump (m^3/h)
Q_{bp}	feed flow rate of booster pump (m^3/h)
Q_{sp}	feed flow rate of supply pump (m^3/h)
P_{bpin}	inlet pressure of booster pump (bar)
P_{hpp}	outlet pressure of high pressure pump (bar)
P_{f-hpp}	pressure of feed flow to the high pressure pump (bar)
P_{f-sp}	pressure of feed flow to supply pump (bar)
η_{hpp}	efficiency of high pressure pump
η_{bp}	efficiency of booster pump
η_{sp}	efficiency of supply pump
N	number of effects
N_{ph}	number of preheaters
$T_{v,i}$	vapor temperature generated in the i effect ($^{\circ}C$)
$T_{v,N}$	vapor temperature generated in the last effect ($^{\circ}C$)
$T_{b,1}$	brine temperature of un-evaporated solution through MED ($^{\circ}C$)
$\Delta T_{eff,i}$	temperature difference in MED effects ($^{\circ}C$)
T_f	temperature of feed water ($^{\circ}C$)
$T_{cw,in}$	cooling water inlet temperature ($^{\circ}C$)
$T_{cw,out}$	cooling water outlet temperature ($^{\circ}C$)
T_s	temperature of low pressure steam ($^{\circ}C$)
$T_{ph,i}$	feed water temperature in the bundle tube of a preheater i
$\Delta T_{preh,i}$	temperature difference between preheaters ($^{\circ}C$)
$T_{db,i}$	un-evaporated brine temperature after flashing ($^{\circ}C$)
$A_{eff,i}$	area of each effect (m^2)

$U_{eff,i}$	total heat transfer coefficient (W
$Q_{eff,i}$	heat transfer provided to the i-effect of MED
M_s	flow rate of low pressure steam mass
M_{prod}	total distillate flow rate
M_f	mass flow rate of feed solution sprayed in 1 st effect
λ_s	enthalpy change related to the vapor condensation
$\lambda_{gb,i}$	latent heat of vaporization
$M_{v,i}$	vapour mass flow rate going to the bundle tube of each effect
$M_{gb,i-1}$	vapour mass flow rate generated by boiling of the brine
$M_{gf,i-1}$	vapour mass flow rate generated by flashing of the brine
$M_{df,i-1}$	vapour mass flow rate generated by flashing of the distillate water
$M_{vh,i-1}$	vapour mass flow rate consumed in preheater
$M_{db,i}$	mass flow rate of the brine solution after flashing

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